

Record books that could be of interest

- KO 11365 .279 (M32) Catalog of Books in the Phillips Library,
Commenced 10/9/1856
- .282 (M35) Eclipse of 7/25/1846 - Portland
- .325 (N42) Measurements of photographs of eclipse 1869-70
- .326 (N43) Measurements of photographs of solar eclipse,
1870
- .327 (N44) Notes to sketches of sun by L. Trouvelot 1870-73
vol I
- .328 (N45) Notes to sketches of sun by L. Trouvelot 1873-74
vol II
- .329 (N46) Solar photography 1870-76. [This is clearly the
record book that belongs to the Winlock solar photos]
- .359 (O27) Notes on the Astronomical Engravings from the
Observatory, Spanish Weather Record, etc. [Phillips Fund]
- .360 (O28) Eclipse of 1869 - Reports [JT says "beautiful volume"]
- .428 Tempel's Comet 1873 - Observations [+ other things]
- 11366 .151 Eclipse Notebook - 1888-1900
- .153 Preparations for Observing Total Eclipse - W.H. Pickering
1886 -
- .242 Halley's Comet Observations - 1909
- .247 24-in Reflector Journal [Clark reflector?]
- .859 Var. + other stars - naked eye observations -
"Contains photograph"

	1	A1	Transit Circle	11/7/1848 - 7/30/1849
	2	A2	" "	7/30/1849 - 9/25/1849
	3	A3	" "	9/26/1849 - 11/29/1849 *
	4	A4	" "	11/30/1849 - 2/6/1850
	5	A5	" "	2/6/1850 - 4/30/1850
	6	A6	" "	5/1/1850 - 10/20/1850
	7	A7	" "	10/21/1850 - 12/26/1850
	8	A8	" "	12/26/1850 - 4/3/1851 *
	9	A9	" "	4/3/1851 - 7/13/1851
	10	A10	" "	7/13/1851 - 9/5/1851 *
001	11	A11	" "	9/5/1851 - 1/15/1852
	12	A12	" "	1/15/1852 - 6/28/1852
	13	A13	" "	6/28/1852 - 12/5/1852
	14	A14	" "	12/1/1852 - 7/8/1853
	15	A15	" "	7/8/1853 - 2/26/1854
	16	A16	" "	2/28/1854 - 8/15/1854
	17	A17	" "	8/15/1854 - 11/27/1854
	18	A18	" "	11/27/1854 - 1/25/1855
	19	A19	" "	1/25/1855 - 5/6/1855 *
	20	A20	" "	5/6/1855 - 7/31/1855
	21	A21	" "	8/1/1855 - 9/25/1855
	22	A22	" "	9/25/1855 - 3/27/1856
	23	A23	" "	3/27/1856 - 6/15/1856
	24	A24	" "	6/16/1856 - 9/5/1856
	25	A25	" "	9/8/1856 - 2/9/1857
	26	A26	" "	2/17/1857 - 9/21/1857
	27	A27	" "	9/21/1857 - 11/3/1857
	28	A28	" "	11/3/1857 - 2/10/1858
	29	A29	" "	2/10/1858 - 7/5/1858
	30	A30	" "	7/5/1858 - 1/24/1859
	31	A31	" "	1/24/1859 - 8/17/1859
	32	A32	" "	8/17/1859 - 1/23/1860
	33	A33	" "	1/23/1860 - 6/23/1860
	34	A34	" "	6/23/1860 - 11/29/1860
	35	A35	" "	11/29/1860 - 3/21/1861
	36	A36	" "	3/21/1861 - 10/1/1861
	37	A37	" "	10/1/1861 - 3/28/1862
✓	38	A38	Meridian	3/28/1862 - 5/7/1862
	39	A39	" "	5/7/1862 - 8/6/1862

001

40	A40	Meridian Circle	8/11/1862 - 9/25/1862
41	A41	" "	9/27/1862 - 12/8/1862
42	A42	" "	12/10/1862 - 2/16/1863
43	A43	" "	2/17/1863 - 5/25/1863
44	A44	" "	5/26/1863 - 8/14/1863

002

45	A45	" "	8/14/1863 - 9/22/1863
46	A46	" "	9/23/1863 - 12/2/1863
47	A47	" "	12/5/1863 - 1/11/1864
48	A48	" "	1/11/1864 - 3/3/1864
49	A49	" "	3/7/1864 - 4/29/1864
50	A50	" "	4/9/1864 - 5/19/1864
51	A51	" "	5/22/1864 - 6/6/1864

52	A52	" "	6/7/1864 - 6/19/1864	unlabeled
53	A53	[" "	6/21/1864 - 7/5/1864]	unlabeled

54	A54	" "	7/6/1864 - 7/19/1864
55	A55	" "	7/20/1864 - 9/9/1864
56	A56	" "	9/10/1864 - 10/10/1864
57	A57	" "	10/10/1864 - 11/4/1864
58	A58	" "	11/10/1864 - 11/23/1864
59	A59	" "	11/25/1864 - 12/20/1864
60	A60	" "	12/30/1864 - 1/18/1865
61	A61	" "	1/20/1865 - 2/1/1865
62	A62	" "	2/2/1865 - 2/25/1865
63	A63	" "	2/27/1865 - 4/3/1865
64	A64	" "	4/3/1865 - 4/26/1865
65	A65	" "	5/1/1865 - 6/2/1865
66	A66	" "	6/3/1865 - 7/4/1865

002

67	A67	" "	7/5/1865 - 7/18/1865
68	A68	" "	7/20/1865 - 8/11/1865
69	A69	" "	8/2/1865 - 8/28/1865
70	A70	" "	8/29/1865 - 9/15/1865
71	A71	" "	9/16/1865 - 9/30/1865

72	B1	Reduction of Transits	1/1/1849 - 8/16/1849
73	B2	" "	8/16/1849 - 12/7/1849
74	B3	" "	12/7/1849 - 4/2/1850
75	B4	" "	4/2/1850 - 10/5/1850
76	B5	" "	10/5/1850 - 12/30/1850
77	B6	" "	12/30/1850 - 4/5/1851
78	B7	" "	4/5/1851 - 7/6/1851

	79	B8	Reduction of Transits	7/8/1851 - 9/4/1851
	80	B9	" "	9/4/1851 - 11/11/1851
	81	B10	" "	11/11/1851 - 2/25/1852
	82	B11	" "	2/25/1852 - 7/6/1852
	83	B12	" "	7/6/1852 - 11/17/1852
	84	B13	" "	11/17/1852 - 5/1/1853
002	85	B14	" "	5/1/1853 - 11/2/1853
	86	B15	" "	11/2/1853 - 4/4/1854
	87	B16	" "	4/4/1854 - 8/9/1854
	88	B17	" "	8/6/1854 - 11/29/1854
	89	B18	" "	11/29/1854 - 1/30/1855
	90	B19	" "	1/30/1855 - 5/6/1855
	91	B20	" "	5/6/1855 - 8/1/1855
	92	B21	" "	7/31/1855 - 9/25/1855
	93	B22	" "	9/25/1855 - 3/30/1856
	94	B23	" "	3/30/1856 - 6/11/1856
	95	B24	" "	6/11/1856 - 8/22/1856
	96	B25	" "	8/22/1856 - 11/20/1856
003	97	B26	" "	11/20/1856 - 4/30/1857
	98	B27	" "	4/30/1857 - 10/4/1857
	99	B28	" "	10/4/1857 - 11/28/1857
	100	B29	" "	11/28/1857 - 2/23/1858
	101	B30	" "	2/23/1858 - 6/24/1858
	102	B31	" "	6/24/1858 - 11/9/1858
	103	B32	" "	11/9/1858 - 6/19/1859
	104	B33	" "	6/19/1859 - 10/14/1859
	105	B34	" "	10/14/1859 - 3/27/1860
	106	B35	" "	3/27/1860 - 11/16/1860
	107	B36	" "	11/16/1860 - 1/1/1861
	108	C1	N. & S. Meridian Marks and Level Readings	12/5/1849 - 4/4/1853
	109	C2	" " "	7/1853 - 4/21/1855
	110	C3	" " "	4/21/1855 - 9/8/1856
003	111	C4	" " "	9/1856 - 2/24/1859
	112	C5	" " "	2/24/1859 - 3/11/1862
	113	C8	Instrumental Corrections	12/29/1863 - 10/1865
	114	C9	Computed AR of Polar Stars	3/11/1862 - 8/19/1863
	115	C10	" " "	8/22/1863 - 11/14/1864
	116	C11	Chronograph Record	6/1861 - 7/1863
✓	117	C12	" "	7/22/1863 - 11/4/1864

	118	C13	Chronograph Record	11/10/1864 - 9/12/1865	
	119	C14	" "	9/13/1865 - 2/20/1866	
	120	C12 [C15]	Misc. time observations		
	121	D1	Minutes of Chronometer Exptd.	4/4849 - 2/1850 #1 -	*
	122	E1	Meridian Circle	11/7/1859 - 5/25/1860	
	123	E2	" "	5/24/1859 - 11/3/1859	
	124	E3	" "	5/25/1860 - 11/13/1860	
003	125	E4	Declinations	12/20/1862 - 9/9/1863	
	126	E5	"	9/14/1863 - 10/17/1864	
	127	E6	New - Transit Circle	2/17/1857 - 5/28/1858	*
	128	E7	Transit Circle	1851 - 1853	
	129	E8	" "	8/7/1851 - 12/4/1851	
	130	F1	Moon Culminations + Transits	12/1845 - 4/1846	(Comets also)
	131	F2	Comets + Meridian Transits	4/1846 - 10/1846	(Earthquake 8/25)
	132	F3	" " "	10/1846 - 4/16/1847	
	133	F4	" " "	4/29/1847 - 2/9/1848	
	134	F5	" " "	2/18/1848 - 8/1/1848	
	135	F6	" " "	8/1/1849 - 2/27/1850	*
	136	F7	Meridian + Prime Vertical Obs'ns	11/6/1844 - 12/12/1844	(EARLY!)
	137	F8	West Transit	11/5/1851 - 12/16/1851	
003	138	F9	Prime Vertical	11/1854 - ?	
	139	F10	Magnetic + Prime Vertical	1858	
	140	F11	Terrestrial Magnetism	3/25/1858 - 6/5/1861	
	141	F12a	[Chronograph	6/8/1864 - 7/21/1864]	
	142	F12b	Prime vertical Computation of Latitude	1864	
004	143	F13	Telegraph	7/6/1848 - 10/28/1848	
	144	G1	Chronometers from July ¹⁸⁵³ 1853 - ¹⁸⁵³ 1855	7/1/1853 - 4/21/1855	(Annular Eclipse 5/24/54)
	145	G2	"	7/1/1853 - 4/21/1855	
	146	G3	Sidereal + Mean Time Clocks	4/21/1855 - 1/1/1856	
	147	G4	" " " "	1/1/1856 - 2/27/1857	
	148	G5	" " " "	2/28/1857 - 7/2/1858	
	149	G6	" " " "	7/2/1856 - 7/16/1860	
	150	G7	" " " "	7/16/1860 - 9/3/1862	
	151	G8	" " " "	9/16/1862 - 3/2/1866	
	152	G ^a	Railroad Time Commenced	6/29/1854 - 10/1854	
	153	G ^b	Trials of Pendulums + Chronometers	4/27/1857 - 2/19/1859	
	154	H ^a	Vol I 517-604	11/1848 - 2/1849 - Comets + Double # 's	1848
	155	H ^a	Equatorial Reductions	6/21/1860 - 1/22/1861	
	156	H1	1-1-1 - 1 - 80	90 - 60 - 20	101 1841 - 7/1847

Equatorial

196	H42	6/22/1861 - 7/13/1861
197	H43	7/13/1861 - 9/12/1861
198	H44	9/16/1861 - 12/30/1861
199	H45	1/1/1862 - 4/18/1862
200	H46	4/19/1862 - 7/5/1862
201	H47	7/6/1862 - 8/19/1862
202	H48	8/19/1862 - 12/2/1862
005 203	H49	12/6/1862 - 4/9/1863
204	H50	4/13/1863 - 6/4/1863
205	H51	6/10/1863 - 10/1/1863
206	H52	10/5/1863 - 2/19/1864
207	H53	2/19/1863 - 3/21/1864
208	H54	3/21/1864 - 6/1864
209	H55	6/1864 - 3/29/1865
210	H56	4/3/1865 - 2/5/1866

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See 284 for more

Zones

211	K1	1-7	4/7/1852 - 5/4/1852
212	K2	7-13	5/4/1852 - 11/3/1852
213	K3	14-19, Bessel	11/4/1852 - 12/14/1852
214	K4	20-26	12/15/1852 - 1/8/1853
215	K5	27-33	1/11/1853 - 2/11/1853
216	K6	34-39	2/12/1853 - 3/15/1853
217	K7	40-45	3/16/1853 - 4/1/1853
218	K8	46-54	4/8/1853 - 5/11/1853
219	K9	55-62	5/31/1853 - 9/8/1853
005 220	K10	65-84a	9/27/1854 - 12/8/1854
221	K11	84a-88	12/8/1854 - 2/3/1855
222	K12	89-100 2/12/1855	2/12/1855 - 4/16/1855
223	K13	101-116	4/23/1855 - 7/17/1855
224	K14	1-6	3/30/1859 - 5/3/1859
225	K15	6-7	5/3/1859 - 5/14/1859
226	K16	117-124	5/23/1859 - 8/25/1859
227	K17	125-135	8/29/1859 - 11/26/1859
006 228	K18	134-146	11/26/1859 - 2/17/1860
229	K19	147-149	2/21/1860 - 11/29/1860
230	K20		11/20/1860 - 2/4/1861
231	K21		2/26/1860 - 4/8/1861
232	K22		4/8/1861 - 6/25/1861
233	K23		7/11/1861 - 10/29/1861
234	K24		0/12/1861 - 1/31/1862

Catalog #'s

	235	K25	Zones	10/22/1862 - 2/10/1863	
	236	K26	"	2/18/1862 - 5/1864	
	237	K27	"	6/23/1864 - [9/29/1864]	
	238	L1	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853	Explanation
006	239	K28	Zones	10/5/1864 - 12/1/1864	
	240	L2	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853	
	241	L3	" " "	1853	
	242	L4	" " "	1853	
	243	L5	" " "	1853	
	244	L6	" " "	1853	
	245	L7	" " "		
	246	L8	" " "		
	247	L9	[Comparisons of Zones]		
	248	L10	Reductions of Zones No Reductions	1859	
006	249	L11	Reductions of Zones Comparison of Magnitudes	1859	
	250	L12	Special Zones and Magnitudes		
	251	L13	Revision of Zones. Magnitudes		
	252	M2	Reduction of Zones-I		
	253	M3	Gould's Universal Index (Catalog?)		
	254	M5	[Tables, Procedures]		
	255	M6	Table of Contents of Various Books containing Records of Observ ^{ions}	1841-1855	
	256	M7	Various Memoranda [Longitude determination, mag. meas, etc.]	1841-58	
006	257	M9	Catalog Stars	1854-58	
	258	M10	Tables for Apportioning Instrumental Corrections	[c. 1855]	
	259	M11	Catalogue of Stars for Zones	[c. 1853]	
→	260	M12	Reduction of Stars in Weisse (?) from 0° to 1° N to 1853		
	261	M13	Printing of Zone Obs ^{ns}	1854 + History & Description of the Obs.	
007	262	M14	Lists of persons + institutions recipients of H. Annals		
	263	M15	Meteorological	1/1/1861 - 5/1863	
	264	M16	1859-60 Comet Seeker	12/1/1859 - 9/11/1860	
	265	M17	Colorado Survey - Time	12/23/1857 - 5/23/1858	
	266	M18	" " Latitude by Polaris	12/23/1857 - 5/23/1858	
	267	M19	[Solar Observations]	" 1/5/1855 - 5/2/1855	
	268	M20	[Catalog of Bright Nebulae + Clusters]	6/16/1850 - 5/1853	
	269	M21	[Comet Seeking]	6/10/1847 - 6/5/1850	
007	270	M23	Books Received at the Obs. of Harw. Coll.	1862-1878	
	271	M24	Reductions of Moon Culminations	1/1849 - 5/28/1852	
	272	M25	" " "	7/1851 - 10/2/1854	
	273	M26	P.S.N. [Tables of ...]	6/16/1852 - 7/4/1856	

	274	M27	[11/15/1850 - 8/22/1851]	
	275	M28	Gould's Universal Index	
	276	M29	Printing 1860 - 1863	
	277	M30	Memoranda for Obs. Report	1/7/1861 - 12/31/1864
	278	M31	Memoranda	1/3/1862 - 1/2/1865
	279	M32	Catalog of Books in the Phillips Library, commenced	10/9/1856
	280	M33	Chronometer - Stars	1862-5
007	281	M34	Transit Catalog	
	282	M35	Eclipse of 4/25/1846 - Portland	
	283	M36	Account of Various Records + Papers belonging to the Obs	- 1864
	284	N1	Equatorial	6/9/1866 - 7/4/1866
	285	N2	"	7/9/1866 - 7/22/1866
	286	N3	"	7/24/1866 - 8/11/1866
	287	N4	"	8/13/1866 - 8/25/1866
	288	N5	"	8/26/1866 - 9/10/1866
	289	N6	"	9/12/1866 - 10/2/1866
	290	N7	"	10/2/1866 - 10/21/1866
	291	N8	"	10/22/1866 - 1/19/1867
	292	N9	"	1/23/1867 - 4/23/1867
007	293	N10	"	4/25/1867 - 10/24/1867
	294	N11	"	10/25/1867 - 1/16/1868
	295	N12	"	1/27/1868 - 4/1/1868
	296	N13	"	4/1/1868 - 10/9/1868 [Spectra]
	297	N14	"	10/10/1868 - 12/19/1868
	298	N15	"	12/22/1868 - 4/22/1869
	299	N16	"	4/28/1869 - 10/18/1869
008	300	N17	"	10/19/1869 - 5/17/1870
	301	N18	"	Misc. Obsns 10/31/1871 - 11/27/1872
	302	N19	"	" " 12/24/1869 - 9/2/1874
	303	N20	"	12/8/1874 - 7/11/1875
	304	N21	Asteroids	7/13/1870 - 12/21/1870
	305	N22	"	2/13/1871 - 8/10/1871
	306	N23	"	(W.A. Rogers)
	307	N24	"	
	308	N25	Reduction of Asteroid Obsns	1870
008	309	N26	"	" " " " 1870-71
	310	N27	Reduction to app. place of some stars used in 1870	
	311	N28	"	" " " " " "
	312	N29	P. 1870	

	313	N30		Search for Asteroids	1870
	314	N31		Equatorial - Obsns of Asteroids + comets (copy)	
	315	N32		Computation of app. place, differ. refract.	Equatorial Comp 2 6/30/1866 - 4/26/1868
	316	N33		Reductions of Equatorial Obsns	10/15/1874 - 6/2/1875
	317	N34	v.1	Equatorial (copy)	4/9/1866 - 8/26/1866
	318	N35	v.2	" "	8/27/1866 - 10/20/1866
008	319	N36	v.3	" "	10/21/1866 - 1/14/1867
	320	N37	v.4	" "	1/14/1867 - 4/26/1867
	321	N38	v.5	" "	4/26/1867 - 10/19/1867
	322	N39	v.6	" "	10/22/1867 - 2/1/1868
	323	N40	v.7	" "	2/3/1868 - 6/28/1868
	324	N41		Catalog of Nebulae (G. M. Searle)	
→	325	N42		Measurement of photog's of eclipse	1869-1870
→	326	N43		" " " Solar "	1870
	327	N44	vol I	Notes to sketches of sun by L. Trouvelot	10/30/1870 - 4/13/1873
	328	N45	vol II	" " " " "	4/14/1873 - 9/30/1874
→	329	N46		Solar photography	7/40/1870 - 11/30/1876
	329a	N48		General record of Work	1869-1872
	330	N50		Tables, etc.	1866-67
008	331	N51		Reduced Measures of Double Stars - E. Equatorial	1866-1867
	332	01		East Transit Observations	5/1/1866 - 9/2/1866
	333	02		" " "	9/4/1866 - 5/24/1867
→	334	03		" " "	5/31/1867 - 11/5/1867
	335	04		" " "	11/9/1867 - 7/10/1868
	336	05		" " "	7/16/1868 - 10/2/1868
	337	06		" " " (Time)	10/3/1868 - 8/22/1869
009	338	07		" " " "	8/29/1869 - 6/6/1870
	339	08		" " " (Occultations)	6/12/1870 - 1/27/1871
	340	09		" " " (Time)	12/1/1871 - 12/27/1871
	341	010		Chronograph Record	4/2/1866 - 7/29/1869
	342	011		East Transit (Errors)	4/17/1866 - 9/17/1867
	343	012		Longitude Campaign: Cambridge - Washington	1867
	344	013		Transit Observations 1867	6/28/1867 - 6/29/1867
	345	014		Formulae for Reduction of Transit Observations + Tables	~1867
	346	[015]		Chronograph Record	7/31/1867 - 12/19/1867
009	347	016		" "	12/19/1867 - 8/14/1868
	348	017		" "	8/19/1868 - 7/30/1869
	349	018		" "	8/13/1869 - 7/7/1870
	350	019		Practical Geodesy and Astrology	1861 - 1869

	351	[020?]	Stars to be Observed w/ East Transit	1868-1870	
	352	020	Second Computation of Instrument Errors	1867-1868	
	353	021	Longitude Computation from Coast Survey	1869	
	354	022	[Transit Observations]	8/24/1870 - 10/23/1870	
	355	023	Longitude - Field Reductions	1871	
	356	024	Clock Corrections	1869-1872	
609	357	025	" "	1872-1875	
	358	026	" "	1875	
	359	027	Notes on Astron Engravings, Spanish Weather record, Phillips Fund		
	360	028	Eclipses of 1869. Reports		[Beautiful volume]
	361	029	Personal equation observations	1871	
	362	P1	Magnetic Observations	8/16/1866 - 2/17/1868	
	363	P2	Meteorological Observations	1866	
	364	P3	" " (?)	1866	
	365	P4	Daily Journal [meteorological]	1867	
	366	P5	" "	1868	
	367	P6	" "	1869	
	368	P7	" "	1870	
	369	P8	" "	1871	("Clayton's Octavo Diary")
010	370	P9	" "	1872	
	371	P10	" "	1873	
	372	P11	" "	1874	
	373	P12	" "	1875	
	374	P13	" "	1876	
	375	P14	" "	1877	
	376	P15	" "	1878	
	377	P16	" "	1879	
	378	Q1	Meteorological Record	1866, 1867, 1868	
	379	Q2	" " of HCO	1869	
010	380	Q3	" " "	1870, 1871	
	381	Q4	" " "	1872-1877	
	382	Q5	" " "	1878-1879, July-Dec 1866	
	383		Mr J.G. Home's Original Minutes of Chronometer Expedition	1857	
	384		A — A — of the White Mts. of New Hampshire	1853 (N.B. Annular Eclipse 1851)	
	385		[Paris to Cambridge Telegraph]	6/20-7/12 ~1861?	
	386		U.S. Coast Survey, Benj. Pierce, Supdt: Letter book + Abstract - Long Party	1868	
	387		Observations and Longitude Computations	1872 (U.S. Coast Survey)	
	388		Longitude + Latitude No. 1 (Bolivia)	1892-93	
	389		T 1. 4/1/1851 - 4/19/1851		

390		Meridian Circle Record - Mr. Austin	8/16/1870 - 5/13/1871
391	Vol 1	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce	3/6/1872 - 3/21/1872
392	2	" " " "	3/22/1872 - 4/5/1872
393	3	" " " "	6/6/1872 - 7/2/1872
394	4	" " " "	5/4/1872 - 5/30/1872 Dup.
395	5	" " " "	5/31/1872 - 6/13/1872 "
396	6	" " " "	6/10/1872 - 6/30/1872 "
397	7	" " " "	6/30/1872 - 7/30/1872
398	8	" " " "	7/30/1872 - 8/9/1872
399	9	" " " "	8/9/1872 - 9/15/1872
400	10	" " " "	8/18/1872 - 3/7/1873
401	11	" " " "	3/9/1873 - 6/7/1873
402	12	" " " "	6/8/1873 - 7/1/1873
403	13	" " " "	9/6/1873 - 9/22/1873
404	14	" " " "	9/22/1873 - 9/30/1873
405	15	" " " "	9/30/1873 - 10/11/1873
406	16	" " " "	10/11/1873 - 2/10/1874
407	18	" " " "	4/13/1874 - 5/3/1874
408	19	" " " "	5/20/1874 - 7/15/1874
409	20	" " " "	7/17/1874 - 8/2/1874
410	21	" " " "	8/3/1874 - 8/4/1874
411	22	" " " "	8/22/1874 - 11/26/1874
412	23	" " " "	11/26/1874 - 12/21/1874
413	24	" " " "	12/21/1874 - 1/14/1875
414	25	" " " "	5/28/1872
415	[paper folder]	Index to books on Meridian Circle Work	1870-1886
416		Fundamental Stars for Zones B8	3/17/1873 - 12/1/1873
417		General Catalog. Obsns + Reductions B1	1871-72
418		Fundamental Stars. Obsns + Reductions. Final Values B1	1870-71
419		Mars. Mars Comparison Stars. ARIADNE Comp. Stars	1877
420		Flexure Constants. Equator Point Corrections	1874-75
421		Instrumental Constants 1870-71, depending on new Pulikowa Flaws	
422		Barometer. Thermometer Runs. Collimation. Flexure	1870-79
423		Refraction Constants. B + T + S	1870-86
424		Obsns. w/ Meridian Circle on 2 mos 50° to 55°	11/16/1870 - 12/16/1870
425		" " " " "	12/16/1870 - 3/28/1871
426		Misc. Tables. Formulae for Zone Reductions	1870-71
427		Misc. Obsns. Transit of Venus. Longitude Montreal - Cambridge	1883
428		Misc. Obsns. Transit of Venus. Longitude Montreal - Cambridge	1877

429		Ruling Machine Screws; Discovery of (112) and (109) + ephemerides	
430		Asteroid 109 - Elements + Ephemeris 1877-78	
431		Orbit of 109, 112 1871-74	
432		112	
433		Planetary Positions (Heliocentric) 1750-1860	
434		Stub? lists (Zones)	
435		Chronograph Record 5/27/1880 - 10/5/1880	
436	A.G.?	Absolute Work Star List - Final List of Dates of Obsms. 1879-81	John A. Dunne
437	Rogers' Work	" " Meridian Circle Obsms. 1879-81	Anna Winlock
438		" " Notebook 1898-1907	Selina C. Bond
439		Posting Book 1897-1908	
440	A.G.	Rogers' Abs. Work - notebook 1904-1911	John A. Dunne
441		Special light Curves with Photometer 1895-96	
442		[Variable Stars ~1897]	
443		Ephemerides of Variable Stars 1896-98	
444		Measurement of Comp. Stars for Variable w/Photometer 1895-1901	
445		[Variable Stars] ~1897-98	
446	I	Obsns of Variable Stars 1890-91	W ^m Maxwell Reed
447	II	" " " 1891-	"
448	III	" " " 1891-92	"
449	IV	" " " 1892	"
450	V	" " " 1892-93	"
451	VII	" " " 1894-95	"
452	VI	" " " 1893-94	"
453	VIII	" " " 1896-98	"
454	IX	" " " 1898-1900	"
455		" " " 1900	"
456		Notebook of Visual Observations - SS Cyg, Nova Per 1899-1902	H.R. Colson, Jr.
457		West Equatorial Observations 4/10/1898-5/12/1899 [SS Cyg]	
458	R	Equatorial Work [Recond of 72 books]	
459	R	Index - Also lists of Variables, etc.	
460	R	Index	
461	R17	Rutherford Millimeter Plate Measurements, etc. 8/16/1897-7/25/1882	
462	R18	Meteorological Observations, etc. 6/23/1880-8/20/1885	
463	R19	Aug - Sept 1877	
464	R20	Aug - Oct 1877	
465	R22	α Ceti, λ Cyg, δ , β Persei 1838-1854	
466	R23	1877-79	
417	R24	Photometric Reductions 1877	

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868

468	R25	Ephemerides of Saturn's and Jupiter's Satellites		
469	R26	Errors of Circles, Misc. Obsns - W. Equatorial		1877-78
470	R28	Misc Obsns. and Reductions		c 1878
471	R29	[Summary of Variable Stars]		1840-1862
472	R30	5	Photometric Observations	1877
473	R31	6	" "	1878
474	R32	c 1878		
475	R33	Observations + Lists		1879-81
476	R34	Form for Eq Observations		1879
477	R35	Prospective Work + Proposed Form of Publication - W. Equatorial		1874-81
478	R43	7		1878
479	R44	8		1878
480	R45	14		1879
481	R46	Photometric Obsns with W. Equatorial		1878-79
482		" " " "		"
483		Description of Procedures + Opt. Setups		
484		" " + Other Obsns		1879
485		" " " "		1879-80
486		" " " "		1879
487		" " " "		1879-80
488		Eclipses of Jupiter Satellites		1878-79
489		Eye + Photom Estimates of Standard Magn		1881
490		Comet Reductions #1		1881
491		" " #2		1880-83
492		26		1881-82
493		28		1882
494		6 1/4"		1882-83
495		15" (?)		1884
496		Comets		1882-88
497		"		1882-85
498		"		1883-87
499		15" (?) Equatorial		1885
500		Comets		1882-89
501		"		1882-94
502		"		1883-87
503		"		1885-88
504		"		1888-89
505		"	Copies of telegrams	1889-98
506		"	(10)	1890

ECP?

Planets and Planets

J.R. Edmunds

507		Comets (9)	1889-90	
508		Journal (Construction of Dome, etc.)	1889-91	R.W. Clifford
509	55		1890	
510	59		1891	
511	51	Hegenschein + Zodiacal Light Obs's (Arequipa)	1891-92	
512	11	Comets	1891-92	
513	56	Journal (Arequipa) #2	1891-94	Andrew E. Douglass
514	62		1892	
515		Comets	1892-99	
516		Parallax Computations #2; Comets	1891-93	
517		Comets + Variable Star Obsns.	1892	
518		Comets (13)	1892-97	
519	67		1892-93	
520	67		1893	
521	68		1893-94	
522	69		1894	
523	70		1894	
524	72		1894	
525		Journal (Cambridge) #3	1893-95	Andrew E. Douglass
526		Variable Stars	1894-95	Wm B. Clymer
527	73?		1894-95	
528	76		1895	
529		Variable Stars 6" W. Eq.	1895-98	
530	77		1895	
531	79		1896	
532	80		1896	
533	81		1896	
534		Variable Stars (Arequipa)	1895-98	Wm B. Clymer
535			1895-98	A. J. Cannon?
536	85?		1896	
537		Variable Stars	1895-99	A. J. Cannon I
538		Telescope Mechanical Notes + Bell Series	1897-1911	Chas. P. Howard
539	94		1897-98	
540			1898-1900	A. J. Cannon II
541		Variable Stars	1899	
542		Variable Star Observations	1899	S. I. Bailey
543		" " "	1899-1902	" "
544			1900-1901	A. J. Cannon
545	122		1901	

u KG11366.
372
recording

124, 125 are
- KG 1366.374
and .375

546	123	1901
547	123	1902-05
548	123	1901-05
549	126	1901
550	127	1901
551	[128]	1901
552	129	1901-02
553	130	1902
554	131	1902
555	132	1902
556	133	1902
557	134	1902
558	135	1902-3
559	136	1903
560	137	1903
561	138	1903
562	139	1903
563	140	1903
564	141	1903
565	142	1903-4
566	143	1904
567	144	1904
568	145	1904
569	146	1904
570	147	1904
571	148	1904
572	149	1904-5
573	150	1905
574	151	1905
575	152	1905
576	153	1905
577	154	1905-6
578	155	1906
579	156	1906
580	157	1906
581	158	1906
582	159	1906-7
583	160	1907
584	161	1907

Notebook # 2

H.R. Colson

Are these
15" record books??

585	162		1907
586	163		1907
587	164		1907-8
588	165		1908
589	166		1908
590	167		1908
591	168		1908
592	169		1908
593	170		1908-9
594	171		1909
595	172		1909
596	173		1909
597	174		1909
598	175		1909
599	176		1909-10
600	177		1910
601	178		1910
602	179		1910
603	180		1910-11
604	181		1911
605	182		1911
606	183		1911
607	184		1911-12
608	185		1912
609	186		1912
610	187		1912
611		15" record	1912-13
612	188		1912-15
613	189		1915-16
614	190		1916
615	191		1916
616	192		1916
617	193		1916
618	194		1916-17
619	195		1917
620	196		1917
621	197	15" Equatorial	1917
622	198	" "	1917
623	199		1917-18

15-inch record books?

15" record

15" Equatorial

624	200	15" Equatorial	1918
625	201	" "	1918
626	202	" "	1918-19
627	203	" "	1919-20
628	204	" "	1920-23
629	205	" "	1926-27
630	206	" "	1928-30
631	207	" "	1934-35
632	208	" "	1935-36
633	209	" "	1936
634	210	" "	1936
635	211	" " (also 12" record)	1936-39
636	212	" "	1936-37
637	1	12-in. Equatorial	1914
638		" "	1915-16
639		" "	1916-17
640		" "	1917-18
641		" "	1919
642		[Box of Papers] II Melens (Leornids)	1898-99 Araguaia Obs.
643		12-in Equatorial - Variable Star Obsns	1919-20
644		" " " " "	1920
645		" " " " "	1920-21
646		" " " " "	1921
647		" " " " "	1921
648		" " " " "	1921
649		" " " " "	1921-22
650		" " " " "	1922
651		" " " " "	1922
652		" " " " "	1922-23
653		" " " " "	1923
654		" " " " "	1923
655		" " " " "	1923-24
656		" " " " "	1924
657		" " " " "	1924-25
658		" " " " "	1925
659		" " " " "	1925-26
660		" " " " "	1925-26
661		" " " " "	1926-27
1.1.7		" " " " "	1927

.758 may
= missing
volume

663		12-in Equatorial - Variable Star Obsms	1927-28	
664		" " " " "	1928-29	
665		" " " " "	1928-33	
666		" " " " "	1934-35	
667		" " " " "	1935-36	
>668	1	[24" Clark Refractor?]	1905-06	[Learn Campbell?]
669	3		1907	
670	4		1907-08	
671	5		1908-09	
672	6		1909	
673	7		1909	
674	8		1909-10	
675	9		1910-11	
676	1	Photometric Observations	1872	C.S. Pierce
677	2	" "	1872	" "
678	3	" "	1872	" "
679	4	" "	1873	" "
680	5	" "	1873	" "
681	6	" "	1874	" "
682	7	" "	1874	" "
683	8	" "	1874-75	" "
684		Experiments with Photometer	1872	C.S. Pierce
685		η Centauri Spectral Study	1911	Leah B. Allen
686	1	Clusters - Spectrophotometric tracings	c 1930	Carol Jane Anger
687	2	α Cyg, Vega	1930-36?	" " "
688	3	" "	"	" " "
689	4	h Per, NGC 663	"	" " "
690	5	Clusters	c 1932 +	" " "
691	6	Clusters	1934	" " "
692	1	Misc; Variables	1918-19	Mary ^D Applegate
693	2	Variables, Map of the Sky	1918-19	" "
694	4	Map of the Sky, Sequences for Orion Neb.	1919	" "
695	5	Asteroids + Novae	1919-20	" "
696	6	Novae + Variables	1920-21	" "
697	7	Map of the Sky	1920-21	" "
698		Daily Journal (13" - Peru)	1889-90	S.I. Bailey
699	25	Double Stars, Planets	1894-96	" "
700	1	Misc; Variables	1917-19	Dorothy W. Block
701	2	Short... Ylmo	1917-19	" "

702	3	o Ceti, Nova Aql 3	1917-19	Dorothy W. Block
703	4	Variables	1918-19	" " "
704	6	Asteroids	1918-19	" " "
705	7	Variables	1919	" " "
706	1	Variable Stars + Meteors	1903	F.E. Brasch
707	1	Variable Stars	1896-98	S.E. Breslin
708	2	" "	1898	" "
709	3	" "	1898	" "
710	4	" "	1899	" "
711	5	" "	1901-02	" "
712	6	" "	1902	" "
713	7	" "	1902-03	" "
714	8	" "	1903	" "
715	9	" "	1903	" "
716	10	" "	1903	" "
717	11	" "	1903	" "
718	12	" "	1903-04	" "
719	13	" "	1904	" "
720	14	" "	1904	" "
721	15	" "	1904	" "
722	16	" "	1904	" "
723	17	" "	1904	" "
724	18	" "	1904-05	" "
725	19	" "	1905	" "
726	20	" "	1905	" "
727	21	" "	1905-06	" "
728	22	" "	1906	" "
729	23	" "	1906	" "
730	24	" "	1906	" "
731	25	" "	1906	" "
732	26	" "	1906	" "
733	27	" "	1907	" "
734	28	" "	1907	" "
735	29	" "	1907	" "
736	30	" "	1907-08	" "
737	[31]	" "	1908	" "
738	32	" "	1908	" "
739	33	" "	1909	" "
740	24	" "	1909-10	" "

779 seems to be first volume here

365.778
= 11366.875

741	35	Variable Stars	1910-11	SE. Breslin
742	[4]	Mag. estimates	1903	[SEB?]
743		Comparison Stars for Variable	1922	L. A. Brigham
744		Variable Stars (?)	1919	G. R. Brooks
745	II	Variable Stars	1901-02	Leon Campbell
746	III	" "	1902-03	" "
747	IV	" "	1903	" "
748	V	" "	1903-04	" "
749	VI	" "	1904	" "
750	VII	" "	1904-05	" "
751	VIII	" " - 5-in	1905-07	" "
752	X	" " "	1907-08	" "
753	XI	" " "	1908-09	" "
754	XII	" " "	1909-11	" "
755		Observations w/ Phot. X on 5-in	1903-06	" "
756		" " "	1903-05	" "
757			1905	" "
758	2		1906-07	" "
759		Photometric Observations	1915	" "
760		6-in (west) equatorial	1917-24	" "
761		Memoranda on Variable Stars	1904-05	" "
762	I	8-in Polar telescope	1908-09	" "
763	II	" " "	1909-11	" "
764		Variable Star Observations	1911-12	" "
765		" " "	1912-14	" "
766		S I 8 17	1911-12	" "
767		Photometer Records	1913-15	
768		Variable Star Observations	1914-15	Leon Campbell
769		log Book - Arequipa Station of HCO	1915	
770		p # 17	1913	
771		Pyrheliometer 17 Observations	1914	
772		Estimate of Work (Arequipa)	1911	
773		Long-Period Southern Variables	1910	
774		Variables	1907-09	{ E. S. Manson H. E. Blackett K. L.
775		Long Period Southern Variable	1904-08	
776	I	" " " "	1918	
777	II	Nova Aquilae No. 3	1918	Leon Campbell
779	[I?]	Variable Star Observations	1900-01	" "
780	IV	Annual Observations	1901-02	

	781	V	Visual Observations	1902-03	
	782	VI		1903-04	
	783	VII		1904	
	784	VIII		1904-05	
	785	IX		1905-09	
	786	X		1906-07	
	787	XI		1907-09	Annie J. Cannon
	788	101	Notes for Reading	1911-39	" " "
	789		Guest Book	1912-35	" " "
	790		Variable Stars, Longitude Determination	1862-82	Seth C. Chandler
Stored under 11366.1080	791				East " "
	792		W Virginis I	1916	C.A. Chant
	793		λ of Sp. lines in red region of stars	1926-27	C.T. Chase
	794	P.D. 1	Spectra of Novae	1926	Paul Dandovich
	795	P.D. 2			
	796	[72]	Journal - lat. + Long. Work	1896	Andrew E. Douglas
	797		Radiometric Book I	1937-38	
	798		Radiometry II	1939-40	Emerson
	799		" Program Bk I	1936-38	" "
	800		Galvanometry Book I	1937-38	
	801	1	Variable Stars	1890-92	W.P. Fleming
	802	2	" "	1892-94	" "
	803	3	" " ; Spectra	1892-94	" "
	804	4	" "	1893-98	" "
	805	5	" "	1894-95	" "
	806	6	" " ; Spectra	1895-99	" "
	807	7	" "	1895-96	" "
	808	8	" "	1896	" "
	809	9	" "	1896-97	" "
	810	10	" "	1897-98	" "
	811	11	" "	1897-1902	" "
	812	12	" "	1898-1903	" "
	813	13	" "	1898-1905	" "
	814	14	" "	1899-1905	" "
	815	15	" " ; Comp. Spectra	1903-07	" "
	816	16	" " " "	1904-10	" "
	817	17	" " ; Photometer	1905-08	" "
	818	18	Novae, Comets, Spectra	1906-11	" "
	819	19	Sh. Plan. M. - Alms	1908-11	" "

820	20	ledger of LPV's	000339-095659		W. P. Fleming
821	21	" "	100661-185905		" "
822	22	" "	190048-235939		" "
823	23	Clusters and Faint Stars		1904-~11	" "
824		Nova Persei Reductions		1902	" "
825	24	Variable Stars			" "
missing 11/1991 826		Measurements of Bright Line Spectra		1890	" "
827	2	Reductions of Photographic Observations		1886-87	
828	3	"	"	"	1886-87
829	4	"	"	"	1886
830	5	"	"	"	1886
831	6	"	"	"	1886-87
832	7	"	"	"	-
833	8	"	"	"	1886-87
834	9	"	"	"	1886-87
835	11	"	"	"	1887
836	12	"	"	"	1887
837	13	"	"	"	1887
838	14	"	"	"	-
839	15	"	"	"	1887
840	16	"	"	"	1887
841	17	"	"	"	1887
842	18	"	"	"	1887-88
843	19	"	"	"	1887
844	20	"	"	"	1887-89
845	21	"	"	"	
846	22	Catalog of E. Stars			
847	23	Description of Spectra			1887-88
848	24	" "			1887-89
849	25	Catalog of E. Stars			
850	26	" " "			
851	27	Discordant Spectra, Remarks on Rejected Measures			
852	28	G Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates			
853	29	E " " "			
854	30	Description of Spectra			
855	31	G Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates			
856	32	Description of Spectra			
857	33	C Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates			
858	34	Catalog of T. plates			

These may all be W.P.F.?

859	35	Reductions of Photographie Observations 1888-90	
860	36	F+G Discordant Spectra	
861	39	Reduction of Photographie Observations	
862	40	Catalog of Plates Classes N, H, L; Peruvian Plates	~1889
863	41	" " " C, D " "	~1889
864	42	Objects of Interest on Spectrum Plates	~1889
865	45	" " " " " "	~1890
866	97	" " So. Bache Plates	1898-1907 W.P. Fleming
867	49	Miscellaneous (Ecl., Solar, etc)	1890-91
868	50	Discussion of Draper Catalog	
869	51	Measurement of Spectrum Plates - So. Draper Cat.	1890-92
870	[52]	Description of Spectra Measures " " "	1890-93
871	53	Discussion of Draper Catalog	
872	56	" " " " " "	
873	57	Catalog of Chart Plates (I-8")	
874	58	" " " " " "	
875	59	" " " " (B in Peru)	
876	61		1892
877	62		1892-93
878	63		1893
879	64		1893
880	65		1893
881	67		1893
882	68		1893
883	69		1893-94
884	70		1894-1903
885		Description of Spectra Measures - So. Draper Cat.	1894-1904
886		Spectra class C	
887		Description of Spectra Measures - So. Draper Cat	1894-1904
888	①	Spectra to be confirmed in cat. of III Stars	
889	②	" " " " " "	
890		Stellar Parallax Stars (13")	
891	③	Spectra to be confirmed in cat. of III stars	
892		Constants in South Draper Catalog	
893		Reduction of Plates Having less than 4 Std. Stars.	
894	(15)	Notes on Draper Cat; Accounts of Share-Holders of The Camera	5/1892
895	81	Measures of Spect. Plates (South Draper Cat)	1903-04
896	82	" " " " " "	1903
897	83	" " " " " "	1903-04

all WPF?

see .566

>898	96	Objects of Interest - Bruce Spectrum Plates	1896-1909	
899	98	" " - Northern	1898-1911	
900	99	" " - So. Bache Plates	1907-1911	W.P. Fleming
901	1	Variables + Halley's Comet		W.S. Franks
902		Colors of 2149 Southern Stars		" "
903	1	Variables		B.P.G.
904	2	"	1912-29	"
905	3	"	1900-20	"
906	4	"	1899-1927	"
907	5	Spectrophotometry of B+O Stars		"
908	6	New Variables	1899-1919	"
909	7	Color Indices of long Period Variables		"
910	8	Spectrophotometry of B + Wolf-Rayet stars		"
911	9	Variable Stars	1900-27	"
912		B Star Observations	1902	Mauds E. Harriman
913		mc plates taken for Standard Magnitude	1908	" "
914		Measurement of Variable Stars	1908	Margaret Harwood
915		" widths of A + B Stars	1922	Marian A. Hawes
916	4	Assorted Plate measurements	1912-18	" "
917		5-in. Equatorial	1918	" "
918	1	Variable Stars	1904-06	{Anson S. Leard Guy Hill
919		Variable Star Observations	1889-1916	E.H. ?
920		Color correction for tel. objectives	1878	Charles P. Howard
921		Assorted Plate measurements		L. Hofrager
922		" " "	1928-30	"
923	1	Measurements of Plates, Stars, etc.	1895-98	Edward S. King
924	2	Reductions of Measures	1899-	" "
925	3	Notes: Photographic Instruments	1904-24	" "
926	3	Measurements: Distances, Altitudes, Plates	1901-02	" "
927	4	Assorted Plate Measurements	1902	" "
928	5	Color distance measurements	1920	" "
929	6	Schilt Photometry	1927-28	" "
930		Photographic Measurement of Light	1897	
931		Computation Book No. 2	1916	Edward S. King
932	1	Photographic Magnitudes, Misc	1914-18	Henrietta S. Leavitt
933	2	Variables, Observations	1902-03	" "
934	4	Examination of Plates	1903	" "
935	5	Variables	1903	" "
936		Phenols	1904	" "

missing
11/1991

937	1	Circumpolar Variables	1895-96	Henrietta S. Leavitt
938	2	Variable Star Observations	1896	" "
939	3	" " " * Plate measures	1896	" "
940	4	" " " " "	1896	" "
941	5	" " " " "	1902	" "
942	6	Circumpolar Variables	1902-04	" "
943	7	Variable Star Observations	1904	" "
944	9	Miscellaneous Observations	1904-10	" "
945	13	" "	1906-16	" "
946	22	Discovery of New Variables	1907-08	" "
947	23	Comparison Stars	1906-07	" "
948	24	Observations of New Variables	1906-07	" "
949	25	" " "	1907-14	" "
950	26	Std. Photog. Magnitudes - T'plates	1907-09	" "
951	27	" " "	1908-10	" "
952	28	" Magnitudes	1909-14	" "
953	29	Std. Photog. Magnitudes - South Pole	1910-12	" "
954	30	" " "	1910	" "
955	32	" " "	1911-14	" "
956	33	Miscellaneous Journal	1911-12	" "
957	34	Miscellaneous	1911-14	" "
958	35	Objects looked up by Request	1914-18	" "
959	36	Standard Magnitudes	1914-19	" "
960	37	Miscellaneous - Comp. Stars	1914-16	" "
961	38	Catalogs (Comparison Stars)	1915-19	" "
962	39	Miscellaneous (Variables)	1915-19	" "
963	40	Discovery of New Variables	1916-20	" "
964	41	Miscellaneous (esp. Novae)	1916-20	" "
965	43	Standard Magnitudes	1919-21	" "
966	44	Miscellaneous (Variables ^{incl. RV Sgr.} 1905)	1920-21	" "
967	1	Miscellaneous Observations - Variables	1893-96	Evelyn F. Leland
968	2	" " " MS	1896	" "
969	3	" " " MS	1896	" "
970	4	" " " MS	1896-97	" "
971	5	" " " MS	1897-98	" "
972	7	" " " WGen	1897-98	" "
973	15	Measures of Eros (South Pole)	1899-1902	" "
974	16	" New Sat. (Phoebe) of Saturn, Nova Sgr	1899-1906	" "
975	25	Measures of M3 etc	1902-03	" "

	976	26	Measures of Eros	1902-04	Evelyn F. Kellogg
	977	27	Search for variables, measures	1902-03	" "
	978	28	" " "	1903-04	" "
See 11366.007	979	30	" " "	1904-07	" "
	980	31 & 32	" " "	1907-09	" "
	981	33	" " "	1904-10	" "
	982	34	Scale Measures (2p. instructions of ECP)	1907-10	" "
	983	37	" " "	1911-12	" "
	984	35	" " "	1910-12	" "
	985	36	" " "	1910-11	" "
	986	38	" " "	1912	" "
	987	39	" " "	1913-14	" "
	988	40	Series Reductions	1913	" "
	989	41	Observing Book - MS	1913	" "
	990	42	Series Reductions	1913	" "
	991	43	" " "	1913-14	" "
	992	44	" " and MS Variables	1914-15	" "
	993	45	" " "	1913-14	" "
	994	46	" " "	1913-15	" "
	995	47	" " "	1914-15	" "
	996	48	" " "	1914-15	" "
	997	49	" " "	1915-17	" "
	998	50	" " "	1915-17	" "
	999	51	" " "	1915-17	" "
11366	.000	53	Measures of Variables in MS	1917	" "
	.001	52	" " "	1916-17	" "
	002	54	" " "	1917-18	" "
	003	55	" " "	1917-18	" "
	004	56	Observing Book	1918-	" "
	005	57	" "	1918	" "
	006	58	Long Exposure H.S. Regions + Series	1918-19	" "
	007	29	New Satellite of Saturn + N. Polar Seg.	1904-11	" "
	008	59	M Determinations - North Pole Plates	1918-19	" "
	009	60	" " " " "	1919-	" "
	010	61	" " " " "	1919-20	" "
	011	62	" " " " "	1919-20	" "
	012	63	" " " " "	1920	" "
	013	64	MF Series	1920	" "
	014	65	" "	1920-21	" "

015	66	MF Series	1921	Evelyn F. Island
016	67	MC and A Plates	1921	" "
017	68	Large Magellanic Cloud	1921-22	" "
018	1	MC Plates	1915-16	H.S. Locke
019	2	" "	1915-16	" "
020	3	" "	1916	" "
021	4	" "	1916, 18	" "
022	5	" "	1916-17	" "
023	6	" "	1917	" "
024	7	Misc. Plates (AC, etc.)	1917-18	" "
025	8	MC Plates	1917-18	" "
026	9	" "	1917-18	" "
027	10	B and MC Plates	1917-19	" "
028	1	Observing Book	1910-19	J.C.M.? Johanna C.S. Macki
029	2	" " (Scale Measures)	1913-18	" "
030	3	" " (MD Plates)	1913-19	" "
031	5	" " (Misc. Plates)	1918-19	" "
032	7	B Series	1919	" "
033	8	Observing Book (B Series)	1919	" also notes? M.K.?
034	9	" " (Misc. Measures)	1919-20	"
035	10	Novae? (Maps of Sky, AC Plates)	1919-20	"
036	1	Observing Book - Variable Stars, etc.	1912-13	Jenavieve F. Mathew
037	2	" " Scale Measures	1913	" "
038	3	" " Series Measures	1913-16	" "
039	4	" " Series, etc.	1914	" "
040	5	" " Miscellaneous	1914-15	" "
041	7	Circumpolar Variables	1914-15	" "
042	8	" " (Est. of Mag.)	1914-15	" "
043	9	Series Measures (principally blue plates)	1915	" "
044	10	" " (" yellow ")	1915-16	" "
045	6	Circumpolar Variables	1914-16	" "
046	11	" " (Est. of brightness)	1915-16	" "
047	12	" " (overflow)	1915	" "
048	13	" "	1916	" "
049	14	" " (Record of Obs. on Photo's)	1916	" "
050		Tables of Ursa Majoris	1894-96	Antonia C. Maury
^{missing // 1991} 051		Rotation of Primary Star & Separation of Satellites	1928-32	" "
052		Formulae for Reduction, Phases in NA & 9	1918-22	" "
053		(Loose Papers) β Lyrae & others	1933	" "

054	1	Obs. Book, Meas. of Variables + Standard Sq.	1912	Mollie E. O'Reilly
055	2	Misc Observations, Variables, Etc.	1914-17	" "
056	3	Scale Meas. of Std. Regions on I series	1913-14	" "
057	4	Circumpolar Variables - Meas. of Comp Stars	1914	" "
058	5	MC Plates	1914	" "
059	6	Meas. of Misc. Plates	1914	" "
060	7	" " "	1914	" "
061	8	MC + Misc. Plates	1914	" "
062	9	" " "	1914	" "
063	10	" " "	1914-15	" "
064	11	" " "	1914-15	" "
065	12	" " "	1915-17	" "
066	13	" " "	1915	" "
067	14	" " "	1915	" "
068	15	" " "	1915	" "
069	16	" " "	1915	" "
070	17	" " "	1915-16	" "
071	18	Southern and AS plates	1915-16	" "
072	19	MC and Misc. Plates	1916-17	" "
073	20	Miscellaneous	1916-17	" "
074	21	Obs. Book -	1916-17	" "
075	22	Southern plates	1916	" "
076	23	Mostly southern regions	1916	" "
077	24	" " "	1916-17	" "
078	25	" " "	1917	" "
079	26	" " "	1917	" "
080	27	Miscellaneous	1917-18	" "
081	28	"	1917-18	" "
082	29	Obs. book	1918	" Sloan
083	30	Scale Measures	1918	" " "
084	31	B series	1918	" " "
085	32	Cat. Sc. Measures	1918	" " "
086	33	For Cat 1° square	1918	" " "
087	34	Cat 4° square	1918	" " "
088	1	8" Polar Equatorial	1910-12	Philip G. O'Reilly
089	2	" " "	1912-13	" "
090	3	" " " (Variables)	1913	" "
091	1	Various Plate Measures		Cecilia H. Payne
092	2	" " "		" "

093	3	Various Plate Measures		Cecilia H. Payne
094	4	" " "		" "
095	5	Wavelength Calculations		" "
096	6	Apertured MC plates		" "
097	7	Emission Lines, Apertured Spectra		" "
098	8	Apertured Arcturus, Vega	c1926?	" "
099	9	Microphotometer, General		" "
100	10	Apertured Altair, Betelgeuse		" "
101	11	Apertured c Stars + Others		" "
102	12	Single Spectra (Capella, Rigel, Sirius, Altair)		" "
103	13	Apertured β Cas		" "
104	14	General Ledgers		" "
105	15	Line Photometry		" "
106	16	Gaertner		" "
107	17	Line Photometry		" "
108	18	Plates		" "
109	20	Apertured Mira, α Cyg, α Per		" "
110	22	Pleiades Background		" "
111	24	Mira, ξ UMa Summary		" "
112	25	K Stars		" "
113	26	Angstrom Magnitudes		" "
114	27	Schilt Microphotometer		" "
115	28	C Stars		" "
116	29	" "		" "
117	30	" "		" "
118	31	B Stars		" "
119	32	C Stars		" "
120	35	Temperatures		" "
121	36	Miscellaneous		" "
122	37	Line Areas		" "
123	38	Long Dispersion Spectrophotometry		" "
124	39	Line Areas		" "
125	40	K Stars		" "
126	42	Line Contours; O stars		" "
127	43	μ ϕ of C stars		" "
127.1	52	Identifications (Sequences)		" "
128	56	Various Plate Measurements	(Under C.H. Payne)	Madelen R. Dwyer
129	56	" " "	" "	Mary L. Miller
130	57	" " "	" "	H.P. M. Torina

131	58	Various Plate Measurements	(under C. H. Payne)	Jenka Mohr
132	61	Plm Grating, Cluster Maps, Sequences		
133		Measures by Bond Astr. Club	under C. H. Payne	1928
134		Various Plate Measures		
135		Miscellaneous.		1877 Edward C. Pickering
136		Correspondence		E. E. Barnard
137	11	Progress of Draper Catalog		
138		Miscellaneous		
139		Various Plate Measures		1890-95
140	1	Misc. Counts for Annual Report		1899-1900 Edward C. Pickering
141	2	" " " "		1908-18 " "
142	1	Misc. Memoranda		1902-12 " "
143	2	" "		1888-95 " "
144		Accident Book		1905-08 " "
145	2	Notebook		
146		Eye Estimates of Stellar Magn. - Instructions		1881 J. Smith
147		Plates + Observations		
148		Measures + Miscellaneous		? Edward C. Pickering
149		Eclipse Measurements		1877 Frank Walde
150		Financial Record + Other Computations		1906 ? Edward C. Pickering
151		Eclipse Notebook		1888-1900
152	45	Determinations of Parallax by Photog. Means		1882 William H. Pickering
153	44	Preparations for Observing Total Eclipse		1886 " "
154		Various Essays		1878 " "
155		" "		1879 " "
156	1	Variables and Asteroids		1914-16 Susan Raymond
157	2	Eros Series Measures, Eunomia Scale Meas.		1916 " "
158	3	Circumpolar Variables		1916 " "
159	4	Asteroids		1911, 17 " "
160	5	Asteroids, Misc.		1917 " "
161		Misc. Observations (under H. H. Plashett)		1875-76 William A. Rogers
162		Plates (Nova Aquilae)		1918 Arthur R. Sayer
163		M-determinations		" "
164		Variable Star Observations		1909-10 L. G. Schmitz
165		Observations of Nebulae		1900 Delisle Stewart
166		Plate Measures		1923? Rufus O. Suter
167		" "		
168		Ols. + Calc. - Ecographical Position		1897? Winslow Upton
169	9	Latitude + Longitude. Arequipa Station		1896? " "

170	1	Scale Measures - series + Chart Plates	1917-18	Mary H. Vann
171	2	Observations of Novae	1917-18	" "
172	3	" "	1918 -	" "
173	4	" "	1918	" "
174	1	Double Star Measures	1876	Leonard Waldo
175		Correspondance	1896-97	Anna Winlock
176		Observations - 6-in Telescope	1911-13	Ida E. Woods
177		SS Cygni	1917	" "
178	1	Instructions, et c.	1915	" "
179		Observations - 6-in Telescope	1913-17	" "
180	4	Cluster Variables	1916	" "
181	5	" "	1917-18	" "
182	6	" "	1919-23	" "
183	7	Examination of AM and AC plates	1919	" "
184	8	Objects suspected as Novae	1919	" "
185	9	Examination of AM and AC plates	1919-20	" "
186	10	Objects looked up for outsiders by request	1921	" "
187	11	New Variables	1921-22	" "
188	12	Examination of AM and AC plates	1920	" "
189	13	Examination of Northern Regions	1920	" "
190	14	Examination of AM and AC plates	1920	" "
191	15	" " " "	1920-21	" "
192	16	Objects suspected as Novae	1921	" "
193	17	Special Objects	1922	" "
194	18	Examination of Southern Regions	1922	" "
195	19	New Variables	1922?	" "
196	20	Special Examination of MC Plates	1922-23	" "
197	21	Nebulae and Asteroids	1923	" "
198	22	Cluster Variables	1923	" "
199	23	" "	1922-23	" "
200	24	Special Examination of MC Plates	1923	" "
201	25	Objects looked up for outsiders	1922	" "
202	26	Special Examination of MC Plates	1921-24	" "
203	27	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1925-28	" "
204	28	" " " "	1924-25	" "
205	29	New Variables	1924-26	" "
206	30	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1924-25	" "
207	31	Cluster Variables	1927	" "
208	32	Misc. Milky Way Regions	1925	" "

209	33	Objects looked up for outsiders	1922-24 ^{02 04?}	Ida E. Woods
210	34	Milky Way Regions, MC+MF Plates	1926-30	" "
211	35	Interesting Objects, Suspected Variables	1926	" "
212	36	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1926	" "
213	37	" " " "	1926	" "
214	38	" " " "	1926	" "
215	39	New Variables	1926	" "
216	40	Misc Milky Way Regions	1927-28	" "
217	41	" " " "	1926	" "
218	42	" " " "	1926	" "
219	44	Objects looked up for outsiders	1926	" "
220	45	Cluster Variables	1927	" "
221	46	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1929	" "
222	47	Dr. Gerasimovic, T Pyx, Shapley LPV's	1927	" "
223		Spectrophotometry, Schilt Measures	1931	G. Maubetsch
224		" " "	1931	"
225		" " "	1932	"
226	140	Variables and Misc.	1905	Oliver C. Wendell
227		A B plates	1934	G. Maubetsch
228	4	Spectrophotometry	1933	"
229		Computation of Ephemerides	1904-07	? Oliver C. Wendell
230	1	Notes on Orion Cluster, Intensities, Betars		CHL
231		Star Sequences	1926	
232		RB Standard Star Identifications		JME + MM
233	3	Chart Plates	1898-99	Louisa D. Wells
234	1	T Andromedae	1916	H.C. Wilson
235		Doubtful Variable, Misc. Obsn's	1904-12	
236		Pyrheliometer Record	1916	W.
237		" "	1917	
238		Variable Star Observations	1902-03	
239	1	" " "	1903	Marion F. Michaelis
240	1	" " "	1904	G. E. W.
241	"	Meridian Photometer	1907	S. M. P.
242		Halley's Comet Observations	1909	
243		Reduction of Observations for Position	1909-10	Oliver C. Wendell + H.C.
244	3	Nova Aquilae	1918	
245		Comparison Stars	1906-09	
246		Calculations - Schaerer + Others	1905, 1911	
247	1	24-in. reflector terminal	1907	

248		Plates, Photometers	1935-36	J. E. Jones
249	94	RH Plates - Photometry	1933	
250		Variable Observations	1907-08	
251		SV Tauri	1925	C. Lanovsky
252	1	Observations	1909	Samuel C. Catterall
253	12	Meridian Photometer	1908	
254	22	Jupiter Eclipses, Variable Stars	1898	
255	23	" " " "	1899	
256	49	New Variable	1926-28	Ida E. Woods
257	54	Evening Cloud Record	1916-17	
258		Shade Glasses	1902-03	C. M. Amstutz?
259	60	Pole Plates (MC) + Misc Experiments		F. Schilt
260	62	Photometric Experiments	1929	
261	63	Variable Star Observations, Photm.	1929	
262	64	" " " "	1929	
263	65	" " " "	1929	
264	66	" " " "	1929	
265	67	" " " "	1929	F. Schilt
266	68	" " " "	1929	"
267	69	" " " "	1929	"
268	71	" " " "	1929	"
269	72	" " " "	1929	"
270	73	" " " "	1929	"
271	74	" " " "	1930	"
272	75	" " " "	1930	"
273	76	RH plates	1930	"
274	77	" "	1930	"
275	78	" "	1930	"
276	79	" "	1930	"
277	80	" "	1930-31	"
278	81	" "	1931	"
279	82	" "	1931	"
280	83	" "	1931	"
281	84	" "	1931-32	"
282	85	" "	1932	"
283	86	" " PTM	1932	"
284	87	" " "	1932	"
285	88	" " "	1932	"
286	89	" " "	1932	"

287	90		R H Plates	PTM	RB	1932	F. Schilt
288	91		" "	"	"	1932-33	"
289	92		" "	"	"	1933-34	"
290	93		" "	"	"	1933	"
291	95		" "	"	"	1933	"
292	96		" "	"	"	1933-34	"
293	97		" "	"	"	1934	"
294	98		" "	PTM	RB	1934	"
295	99		" "	"	"	1934	"
296			Equatorial Observations			1877	
297			Equator Points, Meridian Observations			1877	
298			Telescope Observations			1878	
299	R45		Reduction of Photometric Observations			1878	
300	R47		"	"	"	1878	
301	R48	11	Variable Star Observations, Red'n of Phot. Obs.			1878	
302	R50	12	"	"	"	1878-79	
303	R51	13	"	"	"	1879	
304	R54	15	"	"	"	1879	
305	R55	16	"	"	"	1879	
306	R91	17	"	"	"	1879-80	
307	R92	18	"	"	"	1880	
308	R93	19	"	"	"	1880	
309	R95	21	"	"	"	1880-81	
310	R96	22	"	"	"	1881	
311	R98	23	"	"	"	1881	
312	R99	24	"	"	"	1881	Hersch. S. Webb?
313	R103	29	"	"	"	1882	
314	R104	30	"	"	"	1882-83	
315	R107		"	"	"	1883	
316		38	"	"	"	1884	
317			"	"	"	1885	
318			"	"	"	1885-97	
319			"	"	"	1885-86	
320			"	"	"	1886-87	
321a			"	"	"	1888	
321b			"	"	"	1888	
322a			"	"	"	1888	
322b			"	"	"	1888-89	
323			"	"	"	1889	

Acc 11365.
981

Various?
Variable Star Observations

324					1889
325	57	"	"	"	1889-90
326		"	"	"	1891
327		"	"	"	1891
328	61	"	"	"	1891-92
329		"	"	"	1893
330		"	"	"	1893
331		"	"	"	1894
332		"	"	"	1895
333	78	"	"	"	1895
334	82	"	"	"	1895
335	83	"	"	"	1896
336	84	"	"	"	1896
337	85	"	"	"	1896
338	86	"	"	"	1896
339	87	"	"	"	1897
340	88	"	"	"	1897
341	89	"	"	"	1897
342	90	"	"	"	1897
343	91	"	"	"	1897
344	92	"	"	"	1897
345	93	"	"	"	1897
346	95	"	"	"	1898
347	96	"	"	"	1898
348	97	"	"	"	1898
349	98	"	"	"	1898
350	99	"	"	"	1898
351	100	"	"	"	1898
352	101	"	"	"	1898
353	102	"	"	"	1898
354	103	"	"	"	1898
355	104	"	"	"	1899
356	105	"	"	"	1899
357	106	"	"	"	1899
358	107	"	"	"	1899
359	108	"	"	"	1899
360	109	"	"	"	1899
361	110	"	"	"	1899
362	111	"	"	"	1899

See KG 11365
.531-.533

See KG 11365
.539

W. A. Beckering?

intended in
CG-11365.545

363	112	Various? Variable Star Observations	1899
364	113	" " "	1900
365	114	" " "	1900
366	115	" " "	1900
367	116	" " "	1900
368	117	" " "	1900
369	118	" " "	1900
370	119	" " "	1900
371	120	" " "	1900
372	121	" " "	1900-01
373		Chronograph Record, Zone Stars, 24-in	1877
374	124	Variable Star Observations	1901
375	125	" " "	1901
376	A1	General Catalog, Circle Readings	1871-72
377	A2	" " " "	1871-72
378	A3	" " " "	1871-73
379	A4	Polar Catalog, " "	1872-73
380	A5	" " " "	1872-73
381	A6	" " " "	1872-73
382	A7	General Catalog, " "	1874-75
383	A8	" " " "	1874-75
384	A9	" " " "	1874-75
385	A10	" " " "	1874-75
386	A11	" " " "	1874-75
387	A12	" " " "	1874-75
388	A13	Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars for Zone	1876
389	A14	" " " " "	1876
390	A15	" " " " "	1877
391	A16	Mastklyne Fund. Stars, Circle Readings	1877
392	A17	Circle Readings, Zone Fundamental Stars	1877
393	A18	" " Fundamental Stars	1878
394	A19	" " Coast Survey Catalog	1878
395	A20	" " Fundamental Stars	1879
396	A21	" " " "	1879
397	A22	" " " "	1879
398	A23	" " " "	1879
399	A24	" " " "	1879-80
400	A25	" " " "	1880
401	A26	" " " "	1880

402	A27	Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars	1880	
403	A28	" " " "	1880	
404	A29	" " " "	1880-81	
405	A30	" " " "	1881	
406	A31	" " " "	1881	
407	A32	Fundamental Stars, Observations	1881	
408	A33	" " " "	1881-83	
409	A34	Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars	1883	
410	A35	" " " "	1883	
411	A36	" " " "	1883	
412	A37	" " " "	1883	
413	A38	" " " "	1883-84	
414	A39	" " " "	1884	
415	A40	" " Fund + Zone Stars	1884-85	
416		" " " "	1885	
417	A43	" " " "	1885-86	
418	B1?	" " " "	1877	
419		Observation for Inclination of Declination Wire	1878-79	
420	B3	Polaris Circle Readings + Observations	1879	
421	B4	" " " "	1879-80	
422	B5	" " " "	1880	
423	B6	" " " "	1880-81	
424	B7	" " " "	1881-82	
425	B8	" " " "	1883-84	
426	B9	" " " "	1884	
427	1	Zone measurements	1882	
428	2	Revision of Equatorial Zone	1883	
429	3	" " " "	1883	
430	4	" " " "	1883	
431	5	" " " "	1883	
432	6	" " " "	1883	
433	B1	Fundamental Stars for Zones	1870-71	WSR + AM
434	B2	" " " "	1871	(Augustus McCannell?)
435	B3	" " " "	1871	"
436	B4	" " " "	1871	"
437	B5	" " " "	1872	"
438	B6	" " " "	1872	"
439	B7	" " " "	1872	"
440		" " " (Obscure + Reduction)	1870-71	"

441	F11	Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions				—
442	F12	"	"	"	"	—
443	F13	"	"	"	"	—
444	F14	General Catalog				1871-72
445	F15	"	"	"	"	1871
446	F16	"	"	"	"	1871-72
447	F17	"	"	"	"	1871
448	F18	"	"	"	"	1871-72
449	F19	"	"	"	"	1871-72
450	F20	"	"	"	"	1871-72
451	F21	"	"	"	"	1871-72
452	F22	"	"	"	"	1872
453	F23	"	"	"	"	1872
454	F24	"	"	"	"	—
455	F26	Polar Catalog				1872-73
456	F27	"	"	"	"	1872-73
457	F28	"	"	"	"	1872-73
458	F29	"	"	"	"	1872-73
459	F30	"	"	"	"	1872-73
460	F31	"	"	"	"	1872-73
461	F32	"	"	"	"	1872-73
462	F33	"	"	"	"	1872-73
463	F34	"	"	"	"	1872-73
464	F35	"	"	"	"	1872-73
465	F36	"	"	"	"	1872-73
466	F37	"	"	"	"	1874-75
467	F38	"	"	"	"	—
468	F39	General Catalogue				1874-75
469	F40	"	"	"	"	—
470	F41	"	"	"	"	1874-75
471	F42	"	"	"	"	1874-75
472	F43	"	"	"	"	1874-75
473	F44	"	"	"	"	1874-75
474	F45	"	"	"	"	1874-75
475	F46	"	"	"	"	1874-75
476	F47	"	"	"	"	1874-75
477	F48	Fundamental Stars				1876-77
478	F49	"	"	"	"	1876-77
479	F50	"	"	"	"	1876-77

480	F51	Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions	1876-77
481	F52	" " " "	1876-77
482	F53	" " " "	1876-77
483	F54	" " " "	1877
484	F55	" " (+2ms) "	1877
485	F56	Maskelyne Fundamentals	1877
486	-	Meridian Circle	1875
487	F57	Maskelyne Fundamentals	1877
488	F59	Fundamental Stars	1878
489	F60	" "	1878
490	F61	" "	1878
491	F62	" "	1878
492	F63	Coast Survey Catalog	1878
493	F64	" " "	1878
494	F65	" " "	1878
495	F66	Miscellaneous Stars	1878
496	F67	Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions	1879
497	F68	" " " "	1879
498	F69	" " " "	1879
499	F70	" " " "	1879
500	F71	" " " "	1879
501	F72	" " " "	1879
502	F73	" " " "	1879
503	F74	" " " "	1879
504	F75	" " " "	1880
505	F76	" " " "	1880
506	F77	" " " "	1880
507	F78	" " " "	1880
508	F79	" " " "	1880
509	F80	" " " "	1880
510	F81	" " " "	1880
511	F82	" " " "	1880
512	F83	" " " "	1881
513	F84	" " " "	1881
514	F85	" " " "	1881
515	F90	" " " "	-
516	F89	" " " "	-
517	F88	" " " "	1881
518	F87	" " " "	1881

519	F86	Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions			1882
520	E1	Flexure, Collimation Runs			1879
521	E2	"	"	"	1879-80
522	E4	"	"	"	1880-81
523	E5	"	"	"	1881
524	E6	"	"	"	1881-83
525	E7	"	"	"	1883
526	E8	"	"	"	1883-84
527	E9	"	"	"	1884
528	E10	"	"	"	1885-86
529	A1	Zone Chronograph Records			1870
530	A2	"	"	"	1870
531	A3	"	"	"	1871
532	A4	"	"	"	1871
533	A5	"	"	"	1871
534	A6	"	"	"	1871
535	C6'	Zone Circle Readings			1871
536	A7	Zone Chronograph Records			1871
537	A8	"	"	"	1871-72
538	A9	"	"	"	1872
539	A10	"	"	"	1872-73
540	A11	"	"	"	1873
541	A12	"	"	"	1873-74
542	A13	"	"	"	1874
543	A14	"	"	"	1874
544	A15	"	"	"	1874
545	A16	"	"	"	1874-75
546	A17	"	"	"	1875
547	A18	"	"	"	1875
548	A19	"	"	"	1875
549	A20	"	"	"	1875-76
550	A21	"	"	"	1876
551	A22	"	"	"	1876-77
552	A26	"	"	"	1878-79
553	A25	"	"	"	1877-78
554	A23	"	"	"	1877
555	B1	Polaris, Observations + Reductions			1879
556	B2	"	"	"	1879-80
557	B3	"	"	"	1880

558	B4	Polaris, Observations + Reductions			1880-81
559	B5	"	"	"	1881
560	B6	"	"	"	1881-83
561	B2	"	"	"	1883
562	B3	"	"	"	1883-84

563	C1	Zone Observations + Reductions			1870
564	C2	"	"	"	1870-71
565	C3	"	"	"	1871
566	C4	"	"	"	1871
567	C5	"	"	"	1871
568	C6	"	"	"	1871
569	C7	"	"	"	1871
570	C8	"	"	"	1871
571	C9	"	"	"	1871
572	C10	"	"	"	1871
573	C11	"	"	"	1871
574	C12	"	"	"	1871
<i>missing?</i> 575	C13	"	"	"	1871-72
576	C14	"	"	"	1872
577	C15	"	"	"	1872-73
578	C16	"	"	"	1873
579	C17	"	"	"	1873
580	C18	"	"	"	1873-74
581	C19	"	"	"	1873
582	C20	"	"	"	1874
583	C21	"	"	"	1874
584	C22	"	"	"	1874
585	C23	"	"	"	1874
586	C24	"	"	"	1874
587	C25	"	"	"	1874
588	C26	"	"	"	1874
589	C27	"	"	"	1874-75
590	C28	"	"	"	1875
591	C29	"	"	"	1875
592	C30	"	"	"	1875
593	C31	"	"	"	1875
594	C32	"	"	"	1875
595	C33	"	"	"	1875-76
596	C34	"	"	"	1876

597	C35	Zone	Observations	+ Reductions	1876	
598	C36	"	"	"	1877	
599	C37	"	"	"	1877	
600	C38	"	"	"	1877	
601	C39	"	"	"	1877	
602	C40	"	"	"	1877	
603	C41	"	"	"	1877-78	
604	C42	"	"	"	1878	
605	C43	"	"	"	1878-79	
606	C44	"	"	"	1883	
607	C45	"	"	"	1883-84	
608	C46	"	"	"	1884	
609	C47	"	"	"	1884-85	
610	C48	"	"	"	1885	
611		"	"	"	1885	
612	F91	Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions			1883	
613	F92	"	"	"	1883	
614	F96	"	"	"	1883-84	
615	F97	"	"	"	1884	
616	F98	"	"	"	1885	
617	F99	"	"	"	1885	
618	F100	"	"	"	1885-86	
619	F101	Polar Catalog, Observations + Reductions			1885	
620	F102	"	"	"	-	
621		Collection of Results in Order of Dates			1879-81	
622		Readings of the Sun			1879	
623		Observations of the Sun			1879	
624		Error of Frodsham 1327			1903-04	M. F. Michaels W. W. White
625		"	"	"	1904-05	"
626		"	"	"	1905	"
627		"	"	"	1905-06	"
628		"	"	"	1906-07	J. A. Dunne + W. H.
629		"	"	"	1907-08	W. H.
630		"	"	"	1908	"
631		"	"	"	1901	J. A. Dunne
632		"	"	"	1899-1900	"
633		"	"	"	1896-98	"
634		"	"	"	1902-03	J. A. Dunne M. F. Michaels
1025	T20	Memorable Record			1879-	W. A. Rogers

J1
J2
see 11366.
871 and
872

Chronograph Record

636	J3	"	"	1871	A. McConnell
637	J4	"	"	1871	"
638	J5	"	"	1872	W.A. Rogers
639	J6	"	"	1872	"
640	J7	"	"	1872-73	"
641	J8	"	"	1873	"
MISSING 11/1891	642	J9	"	1873-74	"
MISSING 11/1891	643	J10	"	1874	"
644	J11	"	"	1874-75	"
645	J12	"	"	1875	"
646	J13	"	"	1875-76	"
647	J14	"	"	1876	"
648	J15	"	"	1876	"
649	J16	"	"	1876-77	"
650	J17	"	"	1877	"
651	J18	"	"	1877	"
652	J19	"	"	1878-79	"
653	J21	"	"	1879-80	"
654	J22	"	"	1880	"
655	J24	"	"	1880-81	+ W.V. Brown
656	J25	"	"	1881	"
657	J26	"	"	1881	"
658	J27	"	"	1881-82	"
659	J28	"	"	1883	"
660	J29	"	"	1883	"
661	J30	"	"	1883-84	"

Reports, Meteorological Notes

662		"	"	1889-94	
663		"	"	1886-88	
664		"	"	1883-85	
665		North Pole Reductions		1897-1901	
666		South Pole Reductions		1896-1902	
667	T6	Variable Stars, Computations		1895, 97, 1901	
668		Tabulations of Observations of Variable Stars		1903	
669	T9	Memoranda and Reminders		1896?	
670		Bright Double Stars, Working Lists			
671		Current Relative + Absolute Estimates, Variable Stars		1896	
672		Variable Stars, Computations		1899	
673		Ephemerides of Variable Stars		1902	
674	K1	Clock Errors. Instrumental Corrections		1871-72	W.A. Rogers A. McConnell

675	K2	Clock Errors, Polar Catalog, Instrumental Constants	1872-73	
676	K3	" " General " " "	1874-75	
677	K4	" " " " "	1878-79	
678	K5	" " " " "	1883	
679	K6	Equator Points, Corrections	1871-73	
680	K7	" " " " Flexure, Polar Cat.	1872-73	
681	K9	" " " " Constants	1878	
682	K10	Equator Pt. from Obsns of α + Δ u mi	1876	W. A. Rogers + JFM
683	K12	Copy of Instrumental Constants 1870-71; Redetermin. of $\Delta T, m, h'$	1870-78	
684	K13	Instrumental Constants depending on Pulkovo Coordinates	1871-72	
685	K14	" " " " "	1872-73	
686	K15	" " " " "	1873-74	
687	K16	" " " " "	1875	
688	K17	" " " " "	1876	
689	K18	" " " " "	1877	
690	K 19	" " " " "	1877	
691	K20	Final Values of $\Delta T, m + Reg$ for Reduction of Zone Obsns	1870-74	
692	K21	" " " " " " "	1874-78	
693	K22	" " n and c	1872-76	
694	K23	" " " " " 1870-72	1876-78	
695	K26	Meridian Circle Constants, A, Star Constants	1872	W. A. Rogers
696	K27	Instrumental Constants, Star Constants	1876	JFV
697	K28	Inclination of Declination Wires	1877	JFV
698	J1	DM places for 1855 + 1875; Zone Obsns, Final Red'ns		
699	J2	" " " " " " " "		
700	J3	" " " " " " " "		
701	J4	" " " " " " " "		
702	J5	" " " " " " " "		
703	J6	" " " " " " " Supplement list	1883-85	
704		DM list +53° +54°	1883	
705		" " +50°, +51°, +52°		
706	D4	Thermometer, Barometer Runs	1873	
707	D8	" " " "	1875	
708	D9	" " " "	1875-76	
709	D10	" " " "	1876	
710	R14	Planet + Satellite Observations		
711	R17	Star Observations	1877-78	
712	R18	" "	1877-78	
713	R27	" "	1869 + before	

714	R67	Meteorological Record	1880-82	
715	10	Notes on S.M.P.	1892	
716	12	Micrometer Level	1877	
717	17	Reduction of Observations by Schmidt by Reed		
718	33	Early lists of Gaseous Neb, Stars Pec. Spectra	1880	
719	34	Discussion of H.A. 24, Group M.P. accord to DM		
720	35	" " " " " "		
721	38	Stars + Clusters, Lists with X Plates Entered	1899	
722		Double Stars		
723		" "		
724		Asteroid Zone Book		
725	#3	Eros Book	1893	
726	#4	" "	1876	
727		Zone Stars	1870	
728	U4	Russian Transit		
729	U5	Zone Circle ^{Recordings} Readings	1870	
730	U6	" " "		
731	U7	" " "	1871	
732	U10	D.M. List		
733	U	Brown's Note Book	1880	
734	U	Record of work by D. B. Pratt	1883-84	D. B. Pratt
735	U14	Stars (Zone) Needing Re-examination of chronograph sheets	1871	
736	U15	Stars to be re-observed		
737	U16	Star places	1875.0	
738	U17	1 K'K d d'		
739	U18	3 " "		
740	U19	Zero stars, Red. to apparent place		
741	U20	Table for Reductions		
742	U22	Fundamental Stars, Ephemerides	1879	
743	U23	" " "	1879	
744	U24	Working Lists, Fundamental Stars	1879	
745	U25	" " " "	1879	
746	U27	Longitude Campaign - Obs. + Red.	1872-73	
747	U28	Miscellaneous Observations	1881	
748	U30	Montreal - Cambridge Longitude Observations	1883	
749	U31	Longitude Campaign: Montreal - Cambridge	1883	
750	U34	General Catalog List		
751	U37	? (Bork)	1875	W. A. Rogers
752		Missina		

753	U 40	Chronograph Record		
754	U 41	List of Polar stars w/ dates of Obsn	1885	
755		Flexure Collimation Rune	1880	W.C.
756		Investigations of Circle Observations	1879	
757		Longitude of Circle Errors	1881	
758		Investigation of Circle - Discussion		
759		" of Errors of West Circle from Stops	1884	
760		" of Circle	1877-79	
761		" " Observations	1871-79	
762		Investigation of Errors of West Circle for Stops	1884-85	
763		" " " " "	1885	
764		" " " " "	1885	
765		" " " " "	1885	
766		Investigation of Circle Observation	1879	
767	# 3	Jupiter Ecl. + Var. Stars	1900	
768	# 4	" " " "	1902	
769	# 6	" " " "	1894	
770	# 9	" " " "	1903	RWH
771		Variable? Various Stars Zone P.M. XI		
772		" " " " XII		
773		Arequipa Time Book No. 1	1891-92	J.A. Dunne
774		Chronograph Comparisons	1892	" v. WW
775		Comparison of Waltham Clock w/ Smith Clock	1878	W. A. Rogers
776		Error of Sidereal Clock	1908	WH + J.A. Dunne
777		" " "	1913	Philip O'Reilly
778		" " "	1911	" "
779		" " "	1910	" "
780		Observations	1876	W.A. Rogers
781		Time Book	1875	" "
782		" "	1874	" "
783		" "	1874	" "
784		" "	1874	" "
785		Time Service [Clock Errors?]	1879	" "
786		Clock Errors	1878	" "
787		Time Service	1888-90	
788		" "	1890-91	J.A. Dunne
789		" "	1891	" "
790		" " + Russian Transit	1877	L. Waldo
791		Chron. Record of Stars of N. for Longitude	1871	H. Connett

792	Russian Transit	1883	
793	Time Service, Clock Errors + Russian Transit	1877	L. Waldo
794	" " " " " "	1877	"
795	" " Clock Comparisons	1881	F. Waldo
796	Level of East Transit	1877	L. Waldo
797	Time Service	1887-88	
798	" "	1882-83	
799	" "	1892-94	J.A. Dunne
800	" "	1880	Harriet Wace
801	" " Clock Comparisons	1879-80	F. Waldo
802	" " " "	1878-79	L. Waldo
803	Reference Book: Stars, Asteroids, etc. under observation		
804	Errata in Rogers' AGC Catalogue	1904	J.A. Dunne
805	Meridian Circle - General Record	1879-80	W.A. Rogers
806	Constellations		
807	Working List of Star Data	1871	
808	" " " " for 1880	1880-81	
809	Constellation Data	1879-80	
810	Reduction of Bonn Observations from 1855 to 1875		
811	Discordant Stars		
812	Reports on Obsn of Stars in N. Hemisphere to 9 th mag, Pulkovo	1879	
813	Star Reduction	1890	
814	Measures of Plates	1890	
815	No. 2 Computations - long + lat of Bohmian + Peruvian Stars	1894	
816	2 Zone Observations	1883-84	
817	No. 1 Measurements - WA Rogers Micrometer	1894-97	
818	Sun Images	1880	
819	Miscellaneous Notes		D.C. Bard Bond
820	Chronograph Sheet Readings	1884	
821	Computation of Residuals		
822	Corrections for Error	1869-70	
823	Observations of Southern Variable Stars	1899-1904	
824	Nautical Almanac	1883	
825	Lunar Brightness	1881	
826	XII 12-in Horizontal Telescope records	1899	
827	Satellite IV	1888-90	
828	Reductions		
829	Bibliography		
830	Observations + Reductions Part II	1876	

831		Observations + Reductions, Part III	1876	
832		Re-readings of Chronograph Sheets	1880	
833		Investigations of Division Errors of Circle "East"	1880-81	
834		Chronograph Readings	1881	H. Stevens
835		Readings of Chronograph Sheets	1879	L. Waldo
836		Star Data	1884-85	
837		" "	1882	
838		Star + Comet Data	1881-84	P.C. Ricketts
839		Reductions	1880-81	S.C. Chandler
840		Comet Data + Companion Stars	1881	
841		Time Service	1885-86	W.A. Rogers
842		Dates of Observations of Zone Stars for 1883+1884		
843		Miscellaneous Star Observations		
844		Star Observations		
845		Zone Observations	1884	
846		Fundamental Zone Stars - Circle Readings	1885	
847	J 2	Current Observations of Variable Stars	1895-96	
848		Record of Observations	1898-99	F.W. Thorer
849		Variable Star Observations	1899-1900	H.C. Bailey
850		Absolute Work Runs 1879, 80, 81	1898-99	
851		(Variable Stars)	1883-84	
852		West Dome 6 1/4"	1883	S.C. Chandler
853		" " "	1883	
854		" " "	1896-98	
855		Wedge Zones	1887-	
856		Correction to Ephemeris - Jupiter's Satellites		
857		Final Adopted Maps: Comp Stars for Variables	c/1901	
858		" " " " " "	c/1900	
859		Variables + Other Stars - Naked Eye Obsns.	1889-1890	
860		Variable Star Observations	1894-95	H.C. Bailey
861	19	Variable Stars	1898-99	
862	18	Computation Book	1899-1900	
863	17	" "	c/1902	
864		Wedge Photometer Zone Stars	1894-	
865		Meridian Photometry	1881-84	
866		Multiplet Theory (H.N. Russell) - Notes	1925	
867		Plates to be Examined re. Peters' Zones	1877-78	
868	R21	Equatorial Zones	1877	
c. 9		Identification of Companion Stars for Variables	1894	

870		Crown Flint Optical Data	1902-03	
871	J1	Chronograph Record	1870	
872	J2	" "	1870-71	
873		- chronometer Comparisons	1896-97	R. D. Ward
missing 11/1991 874		Misc. Notes + Work Plans	1862-69	
875	II	Variable Star Observations ($\equiv$ 11365.778)	1901	L. Campbell
876		Thermometer Readings		
877	I	Harvard Lunar Plates	862, 872, 873	Mary Fowler
878	II	" " "	864, 865, 878, 879	"
879	III	" " "	920, 921, 922, 932	"
880	IV	" " "	933, 934, 966, 967	"
881	V	" " "	968, 972, 974, 977	"
882	VI	" " "	978, 979, 1028, 1029	"
883	VII	" " "	1030, 1034, 1035, 1049	"
884	VIII	" " "	1050, 1051, 1067, 1068, 1069	"
885	IX	" " "	1041, 1042, 1043, 1078, 1079	"
886	X	" " "	1080, 1085, 1086, 1122, 1092	"
887	XI	" " "	1093, 1094, 1123, 1124, 1125	"
888	XII	" " "	1126, 1128	"
889	XIII	" " "	1129, 1130	"
890	XV [sic]	" " "	1301, 1302, 1303	"
891	XIV	" " "	1166, 1257	"
892	XVI	" " "	1304, 1305	"
893	XVII	" " "	1307, 1308, 1309	"
894	XVIII	" " "	1310, 1311, 1312	"
895	XIX	" " "	1313, 1314, 1315	"
896	XX	" " "	1318, 1319, 1331	"
897	XXI	" " "	1168	"
898	XXII	" " "	1332, 1375, 1376	"
899	XXIII	" " "	1380, 1381, 1397	"
900	XXIV	" " "	1398, 1402, 1403	"
901	XXV	" " "	1407, 1408, 1412	"
902	XXVI	" " "	1413, 1446, 1445	"
903	XXVII	" " "	1452, 1453, 1462	"
904	XXVIII	" " "	1463, 1518, 1519	"
905	XXIX	" " "	1520, 1521, 1524	"
906	XXX	" " "	1525, 1542, 1543	"
907	XXXI	" " "	1549, 1550, 1590	"
908	XXXII	" " "	1591, 1598	"

909	<u>XXXIII</u>	Howard Lunar Plates	1599, 1606	Mary Fowler
910	<u>XXXIV</u>	" " "	1607, 1662, 1668	"
911	<u>XXXV</u>	" " "	1669, 1674, 1675	"
912	<u>XXXVI</u>	" " "	1682, 1683, 1696	"
913	<u>XXXVII</u>	" " "	1697, 1702, 1703	"
914	<u>XXXVIII</u>	" " "	1737, 1739, 1743	"
915	<u>XXXIX</u>	" " "	1744, 1747	"
916	<u>XL</u>	" " "	1749, 1750, 1751	"
917	<u>XLI</u>	" " "	1759, 1760, 1790	"
918	<u>XLII</u>	" " "	1791, 1795	"
919	<u>XLIII</u>	" " "	1796, 1801, 1802	"
920	<u>XLIV</u>	" " "	1808, 1809, 1826	"
921	<u>XLV</u>	" " "	1827, 1884	"
922	<u>XLVI</u>	" " "	1885, 1889, 1890	"
923	<u>XLVII</u>	" " "	1930, 1931, 1956	"
924	<u>XLVIII</u>	" " "	1957, 1963, 1964	"
925	<u>XLIX</u>	" " "	1973, 1974	"
926	<u>L</u>	" " "	1980, 1981, 2009	"
927	<u>LI</u>	" " "	2010, 2011, 2012	"
928	<u>LII</u>	" " "	2014, 2015, 2074	"
929	<u>LIII</u>	" " "	2076, 2081, 2082	"
930	<u>LIV</u>	" " "	2093, 2094, 2145	"
931	<u>LV</u>	" " "	2146, 2172	"
932	<u>LVI</u>	" " "	2173, 2180, 2181	"
933	<u>LVII</u>	" " "	2184, 2185, 2234	"
934	<u>LVIII</u>	" " "	2235, 2367, 2368	"
935	<u>LIX</u>	" " "	2374, 2375, 2377	"
936	<u>LX</u>	" " "	2378, 2386, 2387	"
937	<u>LXI</u>	" " "	2493, 2494, 2782	"
938	<u>LXII</u>	" " "	2783, 2797, 2798	"
939	<u>LXIII</u>	" " "	2371, 2182, 2368 (Remasura)	"
940	<u>LXIV</u>	" " "	2992, 2994, 3008	"
941	<u>LXV</u>	" " "	3010, 3023, 3024	"
942	<u>LXV</u> [sic]	" " "	1698, 1748	"
943	<u>LXVI</u>	" " "	2751, 2752	"
944	<u>LXVII</u>	" " "	3045, 3046, 3189	"
945	<u>LXVIII</u>	" " "	3215, 3376	"
946	<u>LXIX</u>	" " "	3377, 3385, 3384	"
947	<u>LXV</u>	" " "	3485, 3486, 3535	"

948	LXXI	Harvard Lunar Plates	3536, 3601
949	LXXII	"	3648, 3649
950	LXXIII	"	3669, 3783
951	LXXIV	"	3784, 3811
952	LXXV	"	3812, 3844
953	LXXVI	"	3846, 3856
954	LXXVII	"	3857, 4096
955	LXXVIII	"	4097, 4239
956	LXXIX	"	4271, 4272
957	LXXX	"	4295, 4296
958	LXXXI	"	4297, 4298
959	LXXXII	"	4303, 4304, 4309
960	LXXXIII	"	4336, 4374, 4375
961	LXXXIV	"	4423, 4424, 4455
962	LXXXV	"	4456, 4465, 4466
963	LXXXVI	"	4478, 4481,
964	LXXXVII	"	4503, 4554, 4555
965	LXXXVIII	"	4571, 4572, 4588
966	LXXXIX	"	4589, 4619, 4620
967	XC	"	4677, 4678, 4690
968	CXV	"	7549, 7571, 7572
969	CXVI	"	7665, 7666, 7677
970	CXVII	"	7678, 7692, 7693
971	CXVIII	"	7965, 7966, 7990
972	CXIX	"	8013, 8014, 8052
973	CXX	"	8110, 8288, 8289
974	CXXI	"	8299, 8300, 8306
975	CXXII	"	8307, 8316, 8317
976	CXXIII	"	8346, 8347, 8362
977	CXXIV	"	8635, 8636, 8639
978	CXXV	"	8640, 8904, 8905
979	CXXVI	"	8649, 8650, 8690
980	CXXVII	"	8728, 8729
981	CXXVIII	"	8726, 8727, 8731
982	CXXIX	"	8732, 8890, 8891
983	CXXX	"	9079, 9080, 9086
984	CXXXI	"	9087, 9193, 9194
985	CXXXII	"	9195, 9249, 9250
986	CXXXIII	"	9263, 9264, 9281

Mary Fowler

Martha C Borth

Mary Fowler

Martha C Borth

Note gaps

Haward Lunar Plates

See 1068
for missing
volumes

987	CXXXIV	"	"	"	9377, 9378, 9388	Martha C. Bortin
988	CXXXV	"	"	"	9389, 9413, 9414	"
989	CXXXVIII	"	"	"	9461, 9492, 9491	Ernestine Fuller
990	CXXXVIII	"	"	"	9495, 9496, 9732	Martha C. Bortin
991	CXXXIX	"	"	"	9733, 9754, 9782	"
992	CXL	"	"	"	9783, 9785, 9786	"
993	CXLI	"	"	"	9817, 9818, 9859	"
994	CXLII	"	"	"	9860, 9997, 9998	"
995	CXLIII	"	"	"	10030, 10031, 10072	Ernestine Fuller
996	CXLIV	"	"	"	10073, 10103, [10102]	"
997	CXLV	"	"	"	10227, 10228, 10231	Martha C. Bortin
998	CXLVI	"	"	"	10232, 10263, 10264	"
999	CXLVII	"	"	"	10385, 10386, 10532	Ernestine Fuller
1000	CXLVIII	"	"	"	10533, 10604, 10760	"
1001	CXLIX	"	"	"	10692, 10693, 10701	Martha C. Bortin
1002	CL	"	"	"	10702, 10716, 10718	"
1003	CLI	"	"	"	10737, 10738, 10743	"
1004	CLII	"	"	"	10746, 10748, 10753	"
1005	CLIII	"	"	"	10761, 10933, 10934	Ernestine Fuller
1006	CLIV	"	"	"	10605, 10998, 10999	"
1007	CLV	"	"	"	11004, 11006, 11039	Martha C. Bortin
1008	CLVI	"	"	"	11160, [11161], 11197	"
1009	CLVII	"	"	"	11198, 11201, 11202	"
1010	CLVIII	"	"	"	11208, 11209, 11218	Ernestine Fuller
1011	CLIX	"	"	"	11219, 11276, 11285	" ?
1012	CLX	"	"	"	11286, 11301, 11302	" ?
1013	CLXI	"	"	"	11314, 11315, 11522	Martha C. Bortin
1014	CLXII	"	"	"	11331, 11336, 11337	"
1015	CLXIII	"	"	"	11523, 11542, 11544	"
1016	CLXIV	"	"	"	11549, 11550, 11580	"
1017	CLXV	"	"	"	11581, 11597, 11598	"
1018	CLXVI	"	"	"	11636, 11708, 11709	Ernestine Fuller?
1019	CLXVII	"	"	"	11870, 11871, 11890	" ?
1020	CLXVIII	"	"	"	11891, 11909, 11910	" ?
1021	CLXIX	"	"	"	11924, 11925, 11931	Martha C. Bortin
1022	CLXX	"	"	"	11932, 11997, 11998	"
1023	CLXXI	"	"	"	12017, 12018, 12027	Ernestine Fuller?
1024	CLXXII	"	"	"	12028, 12043, 12044	"
1025	CLXXIII	"	"	"	12068, 12069, 12075	Martha C. Bortin

1026	CLXXIV	Harvard Lunar Plates	12076, 12266, 12267	Martha C. Bortin
1027	CLXXV	" " "	12280, 12281, 12296	" "
1028	CLXXVI	" " "	12301, 12300, 12297	Ernestine Fuller?
1029	CLXXVII	" " "	12323, 12324, 12469	" "
1030	CLXXVIII	" " "	12470, 12474, 12475	" "
1031	CLXXIX	" " "	12507, 12508, 12525	" "
1032	CLXXX	" " "	12526, 12723, 12724	" "
1033	CLXXXI	" " "	12740, 12741, 12774	" "
1034	CLXXXII	" " "	12775, 13018, 13019	" "
^{missing} Vol } 1035	CLXXXIV	" " "	13085, 13274, 13273	" "
1036	CLXXXV	" " "	13109, 13110, 13124	Martha C. Bortin
1037	CLXXXVI	" " "	13125, 13143, 13145	" "
1038	CLXXXVII	" " "	13284, 13285, 13307	Ernestine Fuller?
1039	CLXXXVIII	" " "	13308, 13329, 13330	" "
1040	CLXXXIX	" " "	13609, 13611, 13626	Martha C. Bortin
1041	CXC	" " "	13627, 13641, 13642	" "
1042	CXC I	" " "	13668, 13669, 13716	Ernestine Fuller?
1043	CXC II	" " "	13610, 13645, 13646	Martha C. Bortin
1044	(193)	" " "	13717, 13935, 13936	Ernestine Fuller?
1045	(194)	" " "	13621, 13622, 13140	Martha C. Bortin
1046	(195)	" " "	13142	" "
1047	(196)	" " "	13331, 13332, 13305	Ernestine Fuller?
1048	"	" " Plate characteristics	12017 - 14455	" "
1049	Neptune Plates (Princeton?)		7099, 7534	" "
1050	Neptune	"		" "
1051	Measures of Halands 20406			Fowler
1052	?		4296, 4295	"
1053	Neptune Plates			H.N. Russell
1054	Harvard Lunar Plates		MC650, etc.	H.N. Russell
1055	Supplementary Notes + Data			"
1056	Hayn's Correction for plates of Oct 7, 1911			"
1057	Harvard Lunar Plates		13306, 12319, 12320	Ernestine Fuller?
1058	Neptune Plates			Fowler
1059	Supplementary Notes		3535 - 11998	"
1060	Harvard Lunar plates		14455	Ernestine Fuller
1061	" " "		14448, 14449, 14454	" "
1062	" " "		14408, 14416, 14417	" "
1063	" " "		14399, 14400, 14407	" "
1064	" " "		14095, 14121, 14122	" "

	1065		Haward Lunar Plates	14045, 14046, 14094	Ernestine Fuller
	1066			13959, 14027, 14028	" "
	1067			13914, 13915, 13958	" "
(belongs earlier)	1068	CXXXVI		9421, 9422, 9460	" "
	1069	Fisher	Fireballs - General; Index		PAMPHLET CASE
	1070	"	Correspondance (Lunar Eclipse)		" "
	1071	"	Bright Meteors Reported to HCO 1925-32		" "
	1072	"	Fireballs, Lunar Eclipse		" "
	1073	"	Meteors & Fireballs		" "
	1074	"	Meteors (includes painting)		" "
	1075	"	Meteors, Lunar Eclipse		" "
	1076	"	Meteors, Fireballs		" "
	1077	"	Meteors		" "
	1078	"	Meteors		" "
	1079	"	Meteors (Newspaper clippings)		" "
	1080	—	Observations ~ 1881 ff. - Pickering & Chaudler		" "
	1081	Fisher	Meteor Reports, etc.		" "

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DESCRIPTION OF MATERIALS: Data Notebooks Correlating to Plate Observations

YEARS COVERED: (for example: 1992-1997, 1999) 1896-1940

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Box Number	Records Schedule #	Box Title	Contents Description	Begin Date (MM/DD/YYYY)	End Date (MM/DD/YYYY)
CO 0251	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks	1-19	03/05/1896	10/09/1909
CO 0252	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks	20-21; 23-25; 27-29	03/24/1908	03/11/1914
CO 0253	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks	40-58	02/25/1912	04/09/1913
CO 0254	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks	59-76	01/20/1913	12/20/1913
CO 0255	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks	77-94	12/13/1913	09/17/1914
CO 0256	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks	95-108; 110-114	01/25/1914	05/07/1915
CO 0257	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks	115-133	05/07/1915	10/26/1916
CO 0258	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks	134-152	07/20/1916	03/26/1926
CO 0259	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks	153-168	08/14/1924	11/29/1927
CO 0260	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks	169-187	11/30/1927	02/19/1931
CO 0261	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks	188-201	02/02/1931	01/17/1940
CO 0262	6580	Data Notebooks	000-018	n/a	n/a
CO 0263	6580	Data Notebooks	019-035	n/a	n/a
CO 0264	6580	Data Notebooks	036-054	n/a	n/a
CO 0265	6580	Data Notebooks	055-074	n/a	n/a
CO 0266	6580	Data Notebooks	075-099	n/a	n/a
CO 0267	6580	Data Notebooks	100-122	n/a	n/a
CO 0268	6580	Data Notebooks	123-145	n/a	n/a
CO 0269	6580	Data Notebooks	146-169	n/a	n/a
CO 0270	6580	Data Notebooks	170-190	n/a	n/a
CO 0271	6580	Data Notebooks	191-209	n/a	n/a
CO 0272	6580	Data Notebooks	210-230	n/a	n/a

5 1st tier found #199 HJC in her office 6/30/05. Will return to me.

Vol. 190 has some comments on spectra in Mag. Clouds

variable

Box Number	Records Schedule #	Box Title	Contents Description	Begin Date (MM/DD/YYYY)	End Date (MM/DD/YYYY)
CO 0251	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks 1-19 →	3/5/1896 - 10/9/1909		
CO 0252	6580	Annie Cannon Notebooks 20-21, 23-25, 27-34	3/24/1908 - 3/11/1914	"	
CO 0253	"	" 40-58	2/25/1912 - 4/9/1913	"	
CO 0254	"	" 59-76	1/20/1913 - 12/20/1913	"	
CO 0255	"	" 77-94	12/13/1913 - 9/17/1914	"	
CO 0256	"	" 95-108, 110-114	1/25/1914 - 5/7/1915	"	
CO 0257	"	" 115-133	5/7/1915 - 10/26/1916	"	
CO 0258	"	" 134-152	7/20/1916 - 3/26/1926	"	
CO 0259	"	" 153-168	8/14/1924 - 11/29/1927	"	
CO 0260	"	" 169-187	11/30/1927 - 2/19/1931	"	
CO 0261	"	" 188-201	2/2/1931 - 1/17/1940	"	
CO 0262	"	Data Notebooks	000 - 018	n/a	n/a
CO 0263	"	"	019 - 035	"	"
CO 0264	"	"	036 - 054	"	"
CO 0265	"	"	055 - 074	"	"
CO 0266	"	"	075 - 099	"	"
CO 0267	"	"	100 - 122	"	"
CO 0268	"	"	123 - 145	"	"
CO 0269	"	"	146 - 169	"	"
CO 0270	"	"	170 - 190		
CO 0271	"	"	191 - 209		
CO 0272	"	"	210 - 230		

No.	No.								
	000	—	Visual Obs'ns (Peru)					8/1894 - 7/1896	S. I. Bailey
	001	1	Variable stars in W Cen					11/1898 - 12/1898	"
	002	2	" " W Cen, M5					2/1899 - 8/1901	"
	003	3	" " M3					6/1900 - 9/1901	"
	004	4	" " M3, M5					12/1901 - 9/1912	"
	005	—	" " NGC 7078, 6656, M22					7/1909 - 10/1920	" + Gould
	006	—	Msc. Var. + " " NGC 7078, 6656, M3, M5					1/1902; 4/1910 - 12/1915	"
	007	—	Var. Stars in many clusters					5/1922 - 2/1923	"
10x 362	008	G1	Star counts, Neb. on Mah of Sky, LMC, Glob.					3/1906 - 1/1907	"
	009	G2	Nebulae					1/1907 - 9/1908	"
	010	G3	Nebulae					9/1908 - 10/1911	"
	011	G4	V. I	Position of Nebulae			4/1908 - 7/1908	?	
	012	G5	V. III	" " "			9/1908 - 10/1908	?	
	013	G6	V. IV	" " "			10/1908 - 2/1908	?	
	014	G7	V. V	" " "			12/1908 - 3/1909	?	
	015	G8	V. VI	" " "			3/1909 - 4/1909	?	
	016	G9	V. VII	" " "			4/1909 - 8/1909	?	
	017	G10	V. VIII	" " "			6/1909 - 9/1909	?	
	018	G11	V. IX	" " "			9/1909 - 10/1909	?	
	019	G12	V. X	" " "			11/1909 - 8/1910	?	
	020	G13	V. XI	" " "			8/1910 - 9/1910	?	
	021	G14	1	" " " marked by Dr Shalley		?	7/1923	?	
	022	G15	2	" " " " "			7/1923 - 8/1923	Leon Campbell, Jr.	
	023	G16	1	" " " disc. by D. Menzel			7/1922 - 8/1922	D. Menzel	
	024	G17	2	" " " " "			8/1922	"	
	025	G18	3	" " " " "			8/1922.	"	
	026	G19	4	" " " " "			8/1922	"	
	027	G20	1	" " " Coma-Virgo			2/1927 - 3/1927	A. Ames	
	028	G21	2	" " " " "			1927?	"	
	029	G22	3	" " " " "			1927?	"	
	030	G23	4	" " " " "			?	"	
	031	G24	5	" " " " "			?	"	
	032	G25	6	Draw, Conc. Form "			"	"	
	033	G26	7	Positions, Magn, dia			"	"	
	034	G27	8	" " " " "			"	"	
	035	G28	9	" " " S. gal. Pole			"	"	
	036	G29	10	" " " C.V. ^{opt.} -30° to -60°			"	"	
	037	G30	11	Ident + Mag. NGC Objects			"	"	
	038	G31	12	" " " Coma-Vir ^{opt.}			"	"	

10x
362

2x
53

+R.W. Ford

box
264

box
265

039	G32	13	Plate counts	Coma - Vir etc	?	A. Ames
040	G33	1	Positions of new neb- on A plates		?	C.D. Boyd
041	G34	2	Positions of nebulae		?	S.F. Musrels
042	G35	3	"	"	?	M.E. Musrels
043	G36	4	"	"		S.F. Musrels
044	G37	5	"	"		"
045	G38	6	"	"		M.E. Musrels
046	G39	7	"	"		"
047	G40	8	"	"		"
048	G41	9	"	"		?
049	G42	10	"	"		M.E., S.F. Musrels
050	G43	11	"	"		" "
051	G44	12	"	"		" "
052	G45	13	"	"		" "
053	G46	14	"	"		??
054	G47	A	summary of work accomplished			
055	G48	B	Class + Diagrams			
056	G49	C	Magnitudes of Nebulae			S.F. Musrels
057	G50	D	Class + Diagrams.			"
058	G51	E	Class + Diagrams.			"
059	G52	F	Nebula Counts per Sq. Degree			"
060	G53	G	Magnitudes of Clusters of Nebulae			M.E. Musrels
061	G54	H	Magnitudes of Nebulae			M.E. + S.F. Musrels
062	G55	J	Diagrams of Brightest Nebulae			S.F. Musrels
063	G56	K	Magnitudes of Nebulae			M.E. Musrels
064	G57	L	"	"	"	"
065	G58	M	"	"	"	S.F. Musrels
066	G59	N	"	"	"	M.E. Musrels
067	G60	O	Classifications	"	"	S.F. Musrels
068	G61	P	Magnitudes	"	"	M.E. Musrels
069	G62	Q	Classifications + Diagrams	"	"	S.F. Musrels
070	G63	R	Magnitudes	"	"	"
071	G64	S	"	"	"	M.E. Musrels
072	G65	T	"	"	"	"
073	G66	U	Classifications	"	"	M.E.M. Seyfert
074	G67	V	Magnitudes	"	"	M.M. Seyfert
075	G68	W	"	"	"	"
076	G69	X	"	"	"	"
077	G70	Y	"	"	"	"

↑
box
266

↓
box
267

078	G71	Z	Magnitudes of Nebulae			MM Seyfert
079	G72	A'	Examination of A plates	1936-39		various
080	G73	B'	Magnitudes of Nebulae			M.M. Seyfert
081	G74	C'	" "			"
082	G75	D'	" "			MMS + CDB
083	G76	F'	Revised Nebulae Counts			?
084	G77	G'	Magnitudes of Nebulae			CDB, FWW
085	G78	H'	" "			" "
086	G79	I'	" "			" "
087	G80	J'	Positions	"		? ?
088	G81	K'	Magnitudes	"		CDB, FWW
089	G82	L'	" "	"		" "
090	G83	M'	" "	"		" "
091	G84	N'	" "	"		CDB
092	G85	O'	" "	"		CDB, FWW
093	G86	P'	" "	"		" "
094	G87	Q'	" "	"		" "
095	G88	R'	" "	"		" "
096	G89	S'	" "	"		" "
097	G90	T'	" "	"		" "
098	G91	U'	" "	"		" "
099	G92	V'	" "	"		" "
100	G93	W'	" "	"		" "
101	G94	X'	" "	"		" "
102	G95	Y'	" "	"		" "
103	G96	Z'	" "	"		FWW
104	G97		Examination	"		"
105	G101	Vol I	Coma-Virgo Ext. Magnitudes	1935		J. Cuffey
106	G102	Vol II	" " "	1935		"
107	G103		Nebular Counts	1935-37		Mrs. Lindsay
108	G104		Positions of Nebulae			
109	G105		Magnitudes of Faint Nebulae			
110	G106		Magnitudes of Nebulae	1938-39		C.D. Boyd
111	G107		N.G. Cap Magnitudes			J. Mohr
112	G108		Magnitudes of Nebulae			C.D. Boyd
113	G109		" "			"
114	G110		" "			"
115	G111		" "			"
116	G112		" "			"

	117	G113	Magnitudes of Nebulae	C.D. Boyd
	118	G114	Magnitudes, Diameters of Nebulae	R.L. Paraboschi
	119	G115	Magnitudes of Nebulae	F.W. Wright
	120	G116	Mags. on Overlapping Plates	"
	121	G117 M1	15 th Mag. Survey	J. Mohr
	122	G118 M2	" " "	"
	123	G119	" " "	1935 N.S. Oliver
	124	G125	Classification + Diameter	C.K. Seyfert
	125	G126	" "	"
	126	G127 1	Positions	"
	127	G128	Magnitudes	"
	128	G129	Magnitudes	"
	129	G130	MC Records of Nebulae; Summary	
	130	G131	MC Magnitude of Nebulae	M.E.M
	131	G132	MC Classification + Diameters	
	132	G133	MC Nebula Count	
	133	G134	MC North Polar Cap: Positions	
	134	G135	MC Plate Centers	
	135	G136	MC North Polar Cap: Magnitudes	P.B.J
	136	G137	" " " "	
	137	G138 MCVII	MC Magnitudes	
	138	G139 MCVIII	" "	
	139	G140 MCIX	" "	
	140	G141 MCX	" "	
	141	G142 MCXI	" "	
	142	G143 MCXII	" "	
	143	G144 MCXIII	" "	
	144	G145 MCXIV	" "	
	145	G146 MCXV	" "	
	146	1	Variables in SMC, LMC	1935-39 RK Marshall FWW, VMcK R.A. Craig V.McK. N. A.F. Swain V.McK N
	147	2	" " "	
	148	3	" "	
	149	4	" Vela-Carina	FWW
	150	5	" SMC	1945 A.S. Carlston
	151	6a	" "	
	152	6b	" LMC, SMC	1941, 51 FWW, VMcK S.B., F.W.W., A. Hearn M.D. Ashbrook FWW, VMcK RK Marshall E.M. Corke
	153	8	" "	
	154	9	" SMC	
	155	10	" "	VMcK Nail

box
268

Box
269

	156	11	Variables in SMC, 30 Dor		M. R. Hunt VMcK
	157	12	" " 47 Tuc		VMcK M. S. Matthews VMcKN
	158	13	" LMC, SMC.		FWW et al.
	159	14	" " "		VMcKNail ?
	160	15	" SMC, 47 Tuc, NGC 362		M. B. Leavens M. B. Shapley VMcKN
	161	16	" SMC, LMC		J. Mohr + VMcK
Box 269	162	18	" SMC	1932	VMcKNail
	163	19	MWF 182, MWF 188, SMC, LMC		B. Lindqvist VMcKN
	164	28	M 55, LMC variables	1934	M. Ryden
	165	30	Variables in LMC	1954-55	M. L. Miller J. Swartzman W. Tifft H. S. Kahrut S. F. Marano
	166	31	" "	1952	VMcK, et al. Various
	167	32	" "		VMcKNail
	168	33	" "		FWW?
	169	34	" LMC, SMC	1950 1953-54	FWW et al. FWW et al. FWW
	170	35	Variables in LMC (H.A. 90 #1)		FWW E. F. Heland
	171	FWW1	" LMC		"
	172	FWW2	" " SMC		"
	173	FWW3	" " "		"
	174	FWW4	Red variables "		"
Box 270	175	FWW5	Var's in NGC 1846, 2315		?
	176	FWW Var.1	Var's in ω Cen, NGC 4833, NGC 7099		I. E. Woods
	177	FWW Var.2	Var's in NGC 3201		E. h. ?
	178	FWW Var.3	" " "		
	179	FWW Bk III	Milky Way Bureau, Red Magns		
	180	FWW	Leo I - periods; Vela		
Books in book condition; numbers on front covers	181	11	Variables in ω Cen		
	182	12	" " "		
	183	13	" " "		
	184	17	" " " ; misc. var's		
	185		K Crucis		
	186		Hercules Cluster		
	187	2	Messier 5		
	188		ω Centauri; Eros 2.		
	189	No.1	Measurements of Clusters		
	190	No.2	Discussion of Measures of Clusters		
	191	No.3	Measures of Clusters		
	192	43	Measures Cl. in Per; Obs + Magn.	1903	
	193		Work on Mag. Cls. 1924-25	1924-25	
	194		Var's in Aql, Sct - mostly NA plates	1931-37	

	195	42	Shorthand notes	1921-26	H. Shapley?
	196	42	Cluster in Perseus, Pos + mag.	1903	S.E. Breslin
	197		Variables in LMC	~1931?	S.F. Musells
	198	53	Misc. Variables		F.W. Wright
	199	Z	Variables in Car. + Vel		" "
	200		Measurements at Maria Mitchell		" "
	201		Work on spectra	1921	H. Shapley
Box	202	15	Misc. Var Star Work	1921-46	A. Walker
271	203		Tests on 60-in Telescope	1924-26	
	204	IIa	LMC Variables - mags.	1931	Natalie Ross
	205		Sequences in SMC		A. Ames
	206	S.G. III	SA 194-195; SA 197-199		S. Gaposkin
	207	S.G. IV	SA 196		"
	208	S.G. VI	SA 188-194		"
	209	S.G. V	SA 177-182		"
	210		Star counts of the LMC		M. Miller?
	211		Bright Variable Star Survey, Field 8		?
	212		Measures of Peruvian Pole Star Plates	1901	?
	213	VSF	Variables SA 16, MWF 208, Anticenter 6 01 + 17.6, 122, 190		L.R. Ford Layzer
	214	VSF	" MSF 299, 305, 679 + 298		A.B. Hearsh T.K.
Box	215		Positions of Variables around LMC		M. W.
272	216		Sequences in LMC		
	217		Nebulous Objects in MCs	1953	M.S. Matthews V. McK. Nail
	218		AM Plate Milky Way Atlas		?
	219		Clusters in MCs		H. Shapley V. McK. Nail
	220		"Milky Way Borders" (publ. in HA 106 #3)		H. Shapley J. Sweeney et al
	221		Positions in W Cen		A. Walker
	222	A	O-stars; P-Cygni stars		D. Hoffleit
	223	B	Spectra - η Car and others		"
	224	C	Spectra		"
	225	D	Spectral Classification - Bright Stars		"
	226	E	" "		"
	227	F	" "		"
	228	G	" "		"
	229	H	" "		"
	230	I	" "		"
	231	J	" "		"
	232	K	" "		"
	233	L	" "		"
	234	M	M. S. ? ?		"